

Dissemination Information Pack
COMMUNICATING SUCCESS

Issue Three
August 2021

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INTRODUCTION

The One Health European Joint Programme was launched in January 2018. It is a landmark partnership between 44 partners, including acclaimed food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the Med-Vet-Net Association.

This document should be used as a point of reference, and as a reminder to One Health EJP procedures.

It contains the One Health EJP Communications Strategy, which sets out our vision, aims and objectives, and defines how to effectively communicate these to our audiences. The Strategy allows us to better structure and control information flow to fully exploit the output and outcomes of the One Health EJP.

Any questions and for further information:
OHEJPCommunications@surrey.ac.uk

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OBJECTIVES

Effective communications can contribute to the objectives of the Consortium by:

- building common understanding of audiences and priorities
- helping to explain policy and delivery
- create continuity in communications activity
- articulate objectives and measures of success
- create sustainability.

A crucial outcome of the OHEJP communication strategy is:

- to ensure that the OHEJP is well publicised
- facilitate collaborations between the institutes
- deliver appropriate social and economic impact based on the results
- ensure that results from the project are communicated to target audiences.

Information in a timely and appropriate manner through the established channels is paramount to achieving the objectives.

FLOW OF INFORMATION

The infographic outlines the correct procedure for an effective and efficient flow of information.

HOW WE ARE COMMUNICATING

AUDIENCE	INFORMATION
OHEJP Partners	All internal (including confidential) and external communications
Stakeholders	Internal and external (relevant) communications
Policy Makers	External communications
International bodies	External communications
Scientists - external	External professional communications
Healthcare Professionals - external	External professional communications
Students, Early Career Researchers	External communications
General Public	External communications

Communications Strategy Document

WP1 - COORDINATION

Responsible Partner: UoS

Version: 1 / Issue Date: September 2020

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SUMMARY

Communication is essential for the successful day-to-day operation of the One Health EJP (OHEJP) and to fully exploit the outputs and outcomes. The purpose of this document is to explain and clarify the OHEJP Communication Strategy and provide updated versions of relevant procedures and policies. This document will ensure the communication objectives are met to support the overarching objectives of the OHEJP. The document explains how the communication objectives will be addressed, how the content is tailored, and which communication channels should be selected to communicate with the different target audiences and stakeholders identified. The document also identifies the current challenges, and how the communication team plan to take steps to address each of the challenges. The communication strategy document will be reviewed every 6 months and updated accordingly.

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1. Statement of Purpose

The OHEJP Communication Strategy is essential for the following reasons:

- To ensure that the OHEJP is well publicised
- To promote the communication within the OHEJP consortium is effective to facilitate collaborations
- To ensure that project outcomes have the appropriate social and economic impact based on the results
- To ensure that results from the project are communicated to the appropriate target audiences.

This communication strategy shows how we intend to use effective communications on different platforms to achieve the following aims:

1. To effectively engage with all OHEJP target audiences
2. To effectively engage with all OHEJP stakeholders
3. To advocate and raise awareness of 'One Health'
4. To demonstrate and disseminate the success of the OHEJP work
5. To ensure that those both internal and external to the OHEJP consortium understand the objectives of the OHEJP
6. To change perceptions and behaviour to One Health in the context of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), foodborne zoonoses (FBZ) and emerging threats (ET).

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This document will describe the communication activities listed in the Grant Agreement and how they will support the overarching objectives of the OHEJP.

3. OHEJP Communication Team

Communication Team Members

The Communications of the OHEJP is a Work Package 1 activity (led by WP1 Coordination). The key communication team members are as follows:

Communications	
UoS Leaders	Roberto La Ragione (UoS) Daniel Horton to deputise (UoS)
Communication Team	Piyali Basu - WP6 Communications (UoS) Jade Passey - Digital Communications (UoS) Elaine Campling - Creative Communications (UoS)
WP1 Coordination Team	Arnaud Callegari (ANSES) Hein Imberechts (Sciensano)
Extended Communication Network	
Communication contact person (CCP)	One per beneficiary (<i>See OHEJP consortium spreadsheet available on the private space of the website for the most recent version</i>).

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CCP Network

Communication Contact Person Network:

The CCP network consists of a nominated representative at each of the OHEJP partner institutes. The CCPs need to be utilised effectively to disseminate information within the consortium as they are a key communication avenue within the OHEJP partner institutes. Spontaneous is encouraged by the Communications Team as necessary to ensure that information is up to date and disseminated in real-time.

The role of the CCPs is clearly defined in Annex 1.

Budget has been allocated for an annual meeting with the CCPs at the University of Surrey, in addition to the 0.5 Person Months resource (per institute) to undertake these communication activities. The first annual CCP meeting will be organised in 2020 and will be the first opportunity to introduce and discuss the mandates with CCPs.

Where the CCPs provide the Communication Team with content for dissemination, they will provide Jade Passey (jade.passey@surrey.ac.uk) with 10 days' notice to produce a high-quality communication suitable for the suitable target audiences on social media or the front end of the website. If the information is spontaneous 24-48 hours' notice is required.

Although the Communications Team will communicate with the CCPs on a regular basis, **it is the responsibility of the institute CCPs to update** the team with relevant information.

4. Communications Strategy

OHEJP Communication Support Tools

The following communication support tools have been established:

- Website guidelines have been developed to ensure that members of the consortium can utilise the private space of the website to its full potential.
- Private space of the website has been extensively developed so that members can view and share documents and connect with other members in the consortium.
- Social media guidelines have been developed and will continue to be amended to adapt to the social media strategy.
- Between October 2018 and May 2019, the most effective methods of communication were explored on Twitter and LinkedIn, these methods are now being put into practice by the Communication Team to ensure that the most effective ways to communicate with all target audiences is being utilised.
- OHEJP has been rebranded and the website has been relaunched with this branding, in addition to an updated design.
- [Communication tools](#) have been developed and are available under the "Outcomes" tab on the website:
 - Generic OHEJP Flyer
 - OHEJP brief
 - Official Logos
 - OHEJP Poster
 - Education and Training activities Poster
 - OHEJP Branding guide
 - OHEJP branded conference and event merchandise
 - OHEJP QR Code
 - OHEJP Venn Diagrams.

These tools are available on the front end of the website and are therefore accessible by those internal and external to the consortium, including the general public. The Communication Team is responsible for updating these documents as necessary to ensure the most up to date information is available on the website.

Communications Objectives

The overall objective of the OHEJP is to develop a European network of research institutes, mainly with reference laboratory functions. The OHEJP will integrate public health, animal health and food scientists in

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order to improve research on the prevention and control of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, whilst taking into account the public health concerns of consumers and other stakeholders throughout the food chain. As the consortium is very large and there are different target audiences, an effective communication strategy is essential to tailor and communicate the content appropriately.

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The communication objectives listed here will greatly enhance the effectiveness of communication to ensure the OHEJP delivers its goal and overall vision. To achieve these objectives, the analytics of the social media platforms, Twitter and LinkedIn, and the OHEJP website were monitored monthly from October-May 2019. A short report was produced summarising the analytics and identifying successful communication strategies that have been trailed and tested throughout this period.

The Working Objectives of this strategy are:

- To ensure that the OHEJP is well publicised
Communication objective: To provide regular updates and information regarding the OHEJP news, events, successes, research outcomes and publication on social media platforms, on the OHEJP website and in OHEJP Consortium and External newsletters, to different target audiences.
- Promote the One Health (OH) concept & its importance to general public
Communication objective: To provide and disseminate information regarding the One Health concept and the OHEJP through easy to understand posts, images, infographics and flyers. The External newsletter is targeted towards a wider audience including the general public and includes less scientific language and more images to hold the attention of non-experts. Regular communications at events (by interacting with the general public), on the website and on social media are essential to engage this audience.
- To ensure the results from the Project are communicated to the appropriate target audiences
Communication objective: To provide up to date information on the OHEJP website regarding the scientific outputs from the JIP/JRPs, in addition to highlighting these publications on Twitter and LinkedIn. This will appeal to the scientific community.
Communication objective: To provide scientific updates in layman's terms in the OHEJP External Newsletters and in the Annual Report for Stakeholders. This will appeal to a wider audience including the general public, stakeholders, policy makers etc.
- Promote the One Health (OH) concept & its importance to the scientific community, stakeholders and national politicians and thus create a European One Health Community
Communication objective: To communicate the outcomes of the OHEJP regularly within the OHEJP bodies including PMT, SSB, PMC, POC and CCPs. To also communication with the external stakeholders EFSA, ECDC, COMPARE, EFFORT, JPIAMR and EU-JAMRAI. Communication regarding the OHEJP outcomes as events targeted at national policy makers is also essential, for example the OHEJP event: One Health EJP- How is Sciensano Involved? hosted at Sciensano on the 5th June 2019.
- To ensure the communication within the OHEJP consortium is effective to facilitate collaborations
Communication objective: To communicate on a regular basis with the OHEJP CCPs in each partner institute and to ensure that they are actively engaging with the communication and working alongside the Communication Team to achieve the goals of the Communication Strategy.
- To ensure that project outcomes have the appropriate Translation to Policy impact based on the results
Communication objective: To regularly communicate with all target audiences defined in this strategy, including but not limited to scientists, policy makers, stakeholders and the general public. To communicate regularly with WP5 to monitor relationships and communication with stakeholders.
- Improve the impact of the work generated by the OHEJP
Communication objective: To regularly communicate with the OHEJP governance bodies (for example PMC, POC etc), key stakeholders such as EFSA and ECDC, the External Scientific Advisory Board and the Scientific Steering Board at meetings to ensure that members are aware of the work conducted by the OHEJP and can also disseminate information at their respective levels.
- Demonstrate the success of the work conducted in the OHEJP
Communication objective: To ensure that all events, news, project outcomes and publications are

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well advertised on the OHEJP website, on social media platforms and in OHEJP newsletters. At events such as the ASM, the Communication Team can produce flyers to showcase the successes of the project and display these on a dedicated stand for OHEJP communications.

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Target Audiences

The OHEJP Communications Strategy aims to target a wide range of audiences; this will ensure that the key messages are tailored to each audience. Furthermore, to address the OHEJP key research domains: antimicrobial resistance, foodborne zoonoses and emerging threats at local, national and international levels, content and data dissemination is required to be tailored to educate, inform and effect change in the European Union using a One Health approach.

1. **OHEJP partner institutes** - The members of the OHEJP consortium are at the centre of the OHEJP and most actively strive to achieve the core aims of the project. The 36 consortium member institutes and the Med-Vet-Net-Association (MVNA) represent 19 member states across the European Union, from a range of medical, veterinary and food institutes. This ensures that One Health can be fully integrated into the research conducted by the OHEJP.
 - 1.1 **Strategy to improve overall communications within the consortium**- Where possible, video conferencing should be used instead of teleconferencing as it strengthens communications and relationships between individuals.
 - 1.2 **OHEJP Scientists**- The Project Leaders and scientists that are involved in the Joint Research and Joint Integrative projects are essential to the successes of the OHEJP and their research outputs are pivotal to our impact. Regular communication to our researchers and regular communication of their research is of paramount importance. The Project Leaders will be contacted on a quarterly basis to ask if they have any news or information, they would like to add to the Consortium Newsletters. Furthermore, the Communication Team will send emails regarding workshops or training courses offered by the OHEJP that may be beneficial. The Project Leaders or researchers are encouraged to contact the Communication Team if they have any information, news or events that they would like to be disseminated to the consortium.
 - 1.3 **OHEJP Communication Contact Persons (CCPs)**- The CCPs nominated to enhance the communication across the consortium. The Communication Team works closely with the CCPs to facilitate this (see Annex 1: CCP Mandate).
 - 1.4 **Strategy to improve involvement of lower activity countries within the consortium**- There are a number of ways to improve the involvement of lower activity countries, many of which the Communications Team at Surrey are already implementing. These include personalising emails to the Institute Representatives, SSB members and Communication Contact Persons of these countries as bulk emails are often missed. This has already led to an increase in responses regarding Work Package 6 activities, especially those that are 100% funded by the OHEJP. Furthermore, a spreadsheet has been created to highlight the involvement of all members of the OHEJP. This will subsequently be used to encourage collaboration with partners that have not been actively involved in any of the JIPs, JRPs, ASM and WP6 activities. We recommend that the guidelines for OHEJP WP6 activities could propose that applications highlighting collaboration with low activity countries will score an additional point in the ranking process. The Communication Team will endeavour to create a strong relationship with the CCPs in these countries to increase their involvement.
2. **OHEJP Bodies**- The OHEJP has a number of governance bodies:
 - 2.1 **Project Management Team (PMT)**- the PMT is the main operating body of the OHEJP and consists of all Work Package (WP) Leaders and Deputy Leaders. They are responsible for the day to day management of OHEJP. They are responsible for ensuring the implementation of annual work plan, interacting and reporting to the SSB and implementing decisions of the PMC.
 - 2.2 **Scientific Steering Board (SSB)**- the SSB are scientific representatives of each of the partner institutes. They are responsible for providing strategic scientific advice to the PMT, PMC and POC and selecting the JRPs and JIPs. They are the main executive body of the OHEJP and meet regularly to monitor the progress of the OHEJP activities.
 - 2.3 **Programme Managers Committee (PMC)**- the PMC are Director Generals of each of the beneficiary institutes and are the overall governing body of the OHEJP. They are responsible for all activities undertaken by the OHEJP and for ensuring that the research agenda is consistent with national research agendas.
 - 2.4 **Programme Owners Committee (POC)**- the POC are an external body with which the OHEJP

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must collaborate with to ensure that the activities are aligned with that of the EU and national initiatives. The POC consist of Programme Owner representatives of each participating Member State (for example a person from the Ministry of Agriculture). The POC are responsible for ensuring that the research agenda of the OHEJP is aligned to the Programme Owner priorities and to consider the sustainability of the OHEJP.

2.5 **Project Leaders/ PhD PIs-** the project leaders and PhD PIs are responsible for the scientific outcomes from their projects and collaborating other OHEJP projects and researchers.

3 **Scientists external to the OHEJP consortium-** Scientists globally are adopting the 'One Health' approach and the importance of considering human, animal and environmental health is becoming increasingly essential to address common research goals. One Health is a popular concept in the European Union and is increasing in popularity in less economically developed countries. Engaging with these countries will improve the sustainability of the OHEJP.

4 **Students and Early Career Researchers-** Students and early career researchers are the future for One Health research. Many undergraduates with bioscience, veterinary and medical backgrounds have a limited understanding of the 'One Health' concept. Therefore, through the OHEJP social media activity and Education and Training activities (Doctoral Programme, CPD module, Summer School, Communication and Media Workshop and ASM Satellite workshop) the OHEJP can engage with these students and increase their engagement with 'One Health' and create a One Health community. Similarly, with postgraduate students, familiarising them with the 'One Health' concept may enhance their research. Furthermore, the OHEJP short term missions offer students and early career researchers the opportunity to travel and learn new skills, techniques and methodologies, in addition to initiating collaborations throughout the consortium.

5 **The general public-** the general public have an overall lack of understanding regarding One Health, antimicrobial resistance, foodborne zoonoses and emerging threats despite the fact that they are most at risk. Therefore, the OHEJP must target the general public in order to inform them, for example in good food hygiene practices, antimicrobial stewardship and expose them to the 'One Health' concept.

6 **The Policy makers**

Outputs produced by the OHEJP are primarily intended to scientific stakeholders, the national and European risk assessors, which the latter produce recommendations based on the OHEJP scientific evidences, which are used by the national and European policy makers to define rules and regulations. The policy makers are therefore important actors which need to be kept in the loop of the OHEJP productions.

6.1 **At European level - European Commission's Directorate Generals: DG-AGRI, DG-SANTE, DG-RTD (and DG-ENV in a lesser extent)** cover the scope that the OHEJP addresses. They are the main actors to be targeted. They are contacted and informed or involved on a case by case basis. The Research Executive Agency (REA) manages a Steering Group composed of Representatives of the DGs-AGRI, SANTE and RTD. The REA is the entry contact point to get these DGs informed and involved into the OHEJP activities.

6.2 **At national level - the Programme Owners Committee (POC)**, composed in its overall majority by the Line Ministries of the OHEJP Beneficiaries, in the fields of Agriculture, Health and research. The POC ensures that the activities undertaken by the OHEJP are in line with national interests in terms of research outputs. **In addition, the National Mirror Groups** are bodies that each country voluntarily constitutes to foster interactions between partner institutes, Programme Owners representatives, and any other organisation not member of the OHEJP consortium but acting in the same relevant scientific fields.

7 **Stakeholders-** the OHEJP has a number of stakeholders split into different categories based on the strength, type and level of collaboration:

7.1 **Tight strategic collaboration**, with ECDC and EFSA. This means actively addressing some of their needs, disseminating OHEJP results, keeping the list of stakeholders' needs up to date to be considered also in the long-term strategic research and innovation agenda, and welcoming their advice on the scientific work of the consortium.

7.2 **Lighter strategic collaboration**, with global stakeholders like FAO, OIE, WHO and with European agencies like EMA and EEA and other stakeholders involved in the future. The aim is to keep these stakeholders and agencies up to date with the work of OHEJP, to align the work of OHEJP to international trends and needs and to ensure uptake of results in

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their policies.

7.3 Formal collaboration, with other European projects like COMPARE, EFFORT, JAMRAI and JPI-AMR. The aim of this interaction is to find possible synergies, align the work of OHEJP to their work, so that specific collaboration might be possible.

8 **Practicing Veterinarians, Doctors and health care professionals (external/internal)-** The OHEJP consortium consists of institutes with medical, veterinary and food expertise to ensure that it truly addresses 'One Health'. This will strengthen the OHEJP's ability to reach healthcare professions in all sectors. These audiences are often targeted for inappropriate use of antibiotics for example, therefore by working to inform healthcare practise through research into diagnostic tests, and dissemination of this information the OHEJP could work with these healthcare professionals to improve diagnostics and prescribing habits.

OHEJP Governance

Strategies to target these audiences:

Target Audience	OHEJP activities of interest	Targeted Strategy
OHEJP partners	All areas of the OHEJP including but not limited to the JIPs/JRPs, Work Package 6 (WP6) Education and Training Activities, events, meetings, OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM), events, open access data, capacity map.	Those internal to the consortium are targeted through regular email communication both directly and indirectly through the Communication Contact Person network. There is a quarterly Consortium Newsletter that is sent internally which updates members on the OHEJP, key events and important dates. Additionally, there is a monthly WP6 bulletin to update on all funding calls and WP6 events. Members have access to the private space of the website which contains important documents and information for the members. The OHEJP also interact with consortium members on social media. The JIPs and JRPs, Education and Training activities and other OHEJP workshops are available to all consortium members to progress their career and teach new skills.
Scientists external to the OHEJP	Updates of the JIPs/JRPs, Education and Training activities, events, collaborations, OHEJP ASM, workshops, open access data and publications, the OHEJP SRA, capacity map.	Those external to the consortium have access to the front end of the website and the OHEJP social media accounts, which are updated regularly. The Consortium Newsletters and External Newsletters are also uploaded on to the 'Newsletters' page of the website. These newsletter is not only targeted to internal members and scientists but is written with external scientists in mind also. Additionally, there is a monthly WP6 bulletin to update on all events. Annually, the OHEJP has an annual scientific meeting where experts in the One Health field are encouraged to attend. A number of workshops hosted by different work packages are also open to those external to the consortium.
Students and Early Career Researchers (ECR)	Education and Training activities, workshops and opportunities to collaborate with the OHEJP consortium.	Students and ECRs within the consortium have access to all workshops and Education and Training activities such as the Doctoral Programme, Summer School, Short Term Missions, the CPD module, the ASM Satellite Workshop and the Communication and Media workshop. All information regarding these events is initially disseminated to the Project Management team, Scientific Steering Board, Project Leaders and Communication Contact Persons via a monthly bulletin, who are required to forward the information on to the ECRs and PhD students who may be interested in attending these events. These events will be extensively advertised on social media platforms using targeted hashtags to appeal PhD students and ECRs (see social media strategy). The front end of the website has also been designed to be a more interactive and informative platform for students and ECRs to find information and eligibility criteria. Each of the calls has a designated group on the OHEJP private space, therefore applicants are encouraged to register to the website to view documentation that is not on the front end of the website.

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<p>The general public</p>	<p>Understanding the One Health approach, updates for the OHEJP in simplified and engaging language.</p>	<p>The general public are primarily targeted through social media channels as described below, in the social media strategy. There are a number of hashtags that have a higher interaction from the general public that are more generic than the scientific hashtags identified. There is also a biannual OHEJP External Newsletter that is sent to an external mailing list which individual can sign up to on the website. This list currently has approximately 500 subscribers. The External Newsletter uses simpler language compared to the Consortium newsletter, and is shorter in length, therefore is in a more manageable format for the general public. It contains more images and links to the OHEJP website and consortium member websites to encourage individuals to continuing reading topics that interest them. The OHEJP Communication Team have also created a branded OHEJP brief and flyer which were designed in such a way that they would appeal to the general public.</p>
<p>European policy makers (EC DGs)</p>	<p>Discuss and present the OHEJP plans and achievement periodically, notably through the REA Steering group meetings</p>	<p>In addition to the regular REA Steering Group meetings held with the EC DGs and the POC meetings, efforts should be made to systematically think of informing them of any significant development and/or progress in the OHEJP work. Indeed, although the policy makers are indirect stakeholders, they remain the ultimate end-users of the outputs produced by the OHEJP. Constant effort should therefore be made into demonstrating to them what is the added-value that the OHEJP can bring to their own regulation activities. This can be achieved in involving them into strategic meetings with the OHEJP direct stakeholders or inviting them to the OHEJP ASMs.</p>
<p>National policy makers (Line Ministries)</p>	<p>Discuss and present the OHEJP plans and achievement periodically through the POC meetings</p>	<p>There are open access data points on the OHEJP website that allow stakeholders to monitor the process of the programme. Additionally, there will be pages on the website that contain the OHEJP and project deliverables so that this progress can also be monitored. Stakeholder Committee meetings are also organised twice a year. OHEJP stakeholders also have access to the OHEJP newsletters. These are disseminated using Stakeholder mailing lists and are also uploaded on to the front end of the website. The Communication Team and WP5 Leader/Deputy Leader/ Collaborators will also encourage stakeholders to sign up to the external newsletter from the OHEJP website. WP5 also publish targeted reports for the stakeholders which highlight OHEJP outcomes and identify possible synergies.</p>
<p>Stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC, JPI AMR, EU-JAM-RAI, COM-PARE, EFFORT, WHO-Europe, FAO, EEA, EMA)</p>	<p>Updates from JIPs/ JRPs, Work Package 7 sustainability, stakeholder's meetings, events, the OHEJP ASM, data management to avoid duplication of work across to EU, the OHEJP SRA, the translation of science to policy, targeted reports from WP5, helpdesk, OHEJP Outcome Inventory.</p>	<p>Publications from the OHEJP JIPs/JRPs are uploaded on to the OHEJP website, in addition to having open access data points on the project pages. These publications may be able to influence medical practices and improve diagnostic and antibiotic stewardship for example. The scientific outcomes are also reported annually in the 'Annual Report for Stakeholders', which is in a readable format for all target audiences. Workshops and events such as the ASM are platforms to showcase One Health research and to initiate conversations and collaborations. The OHEJP also aims to translate science to policy (WP5), therefore ultimately targeting healthcare professions through changes in methodologies etc. Quarterly consortium newsletters are also targeted to this audience to regularly update and highlight the work we are doing to gain their interest and investment into looking at our data from the project when available.</p>
<p>Healthcare professionals (Doctors, Veterinarians etc)</p>	<p>The translation of science conducted in the JIPs/JRPs to their medical practices, updates from the JIPs/JRPs, events, the OHEJP ASM, Workshops, the translation of science to policy.</p>	<p>Publications from the OHEJP JIPs/JRPs are uploaded on to the OHEJP website, in addition to having open access data points on the project pages. These publications may be able to influence medical practices and improve diagnostic and antibiotic stewardship for example. The scientific outcomes are also reported annually in the 'Annual Report for Stakeholders', which is in a readable format for all target audiences. Workshops and events such as the ASM are platforms to showcase One Health research and to initiate conversations and collaborations. The OHEJP also aims to translate science to policy (WP5), therefore ultimately targeting healthcare professions through changes in methodologies etc. Quarterly consortium newsletters are also targeted to this audience to regularly update and highlight the work we are doing to gain their interest and investment into looking at our data from the project when available.</p>

<p>International agencies (WHO, FAO, OIE)</p>	<p>The outputs from the JIPs/JRPs and the translation of science to policy. The harmonisation of approaches, not just in the EU, but also globally.</p>	<p>An annual report from the OHEJP is produced each year and made publicly available. This report includes the overall outcomes from the OHEJP and also the scientific outcomes. The SRA is also publicly available, therefore international bodies such as WHO, FAO and OIE can access this document to read about the OHEJP research agenda and how it may align with their own agenda. Targeted reports to reflect how some needs are addressed by the OHEJP There are calls from WHO, FAO, OIE to contribute to their research/documentation. Where these are advertised, the Communication Team will forward this to the consortium to encourage their participation. This will increase the visibility of the OHEJP. The JIPs are in collaboration with these international bodies, therefore it is evident that the SRA and Integrative Activities have successfully initiated this collaboration.</p>
<p>OHEJP Governance Bodies: PMT, PMC, SSB etc.</p>	<p>All updates from the OHEJP</p>	<p>There are number of annual/biannual meetings for the governance bodies of the OHEJP. The meetings provide a platform for a face to face meeting between the PMT and these governance bodies. In between these meetings, these bodies are included in the Newsletter mailing lists, including the WP6 bulletin. Under special circumstances, the relevant governance bodies will be emailed specific information that is important, however the Communication Team aim to keep these emails to a minimum.</p>

Communication Action Plan

An action plan has been devised (see below) and will be regularly updated throughout the Project lifetime.

Action	Who is responsible?	When will this be produced?	What frequency?	KPI
<p>Review, amend and update all communication procedures and policies throughout the lifetime of the project</p>	<p>Communication Team</p>	<p>February and August each year</p>	<p>Every 6 months or as required if there is a significant change</p>	<p>Production of updated versions of the communication strategy and any relevant documentation in February and August</p>
<p>Development of existing webpages</p>	<p>Digital Communication</p>	<p>As necessary for example if content changes or additional features are requested from the consortium</p>	<p>As necessary for example if content changes or additional features are requested from the consortium</p>	<p>Publication of final updated web pages on the OHEJP website</p>
<p>Creation, design content of new webpages</p>	<p>Digital Communication</p>	<p>Ongoing throughout the lifetime of the project</p>	<p>Ongoing throughout the lifetime of the project</p>	<p>Collaborate with the One Health Platform and One Health Commission Maintain contact with previous event attendees, for example adding them to newsletter mailing lists with their permission Creating event hashtags for social media to create a strong social media presence</p>

Creation of an online One Health Community	Digital Communication	Ongoing throughout the lifetime of the project	Ongoing throughout the lifetime of the project	Collaborate with the One Health Platform and One Health Commission Maintain contact with previous event attendees, for example adding them to newsletter mailing lists with their permission Creating event hashtags for social media to create a strong social media presence
Reporting of statistics associated with the website and social media accounts	Digital Communication	June each year	Annual	Production of a document detailing the website and social media statistics and the success of previously determined KPIs
Final report of all communication activities with compiled evidence	Communication Team	December 2022	Once, at the end of the OHEJP	Production of a report that will be submitted to the OHEJP Coordinators
Publish consortium newsletters	Digital Communication	February, June, September, December	Every quarter	Production of each newsletter sent using MailChimp
Publish external newsletters	Digital Communication	July (before the summer break) and December (before the Christmas break)	Bi- annually	Production of each newsletter sent using MailChimp
Publish special issue on One Health Zoonoses	Communication Team and PMT	June 2022	Once, at the end of the OHEJP	Publication in a relevant scientific journal for example Medical Microbiology One Health section
Any important outcomes from the OHEJP, such as the ASM or Summer School etc will be communicated through press release	Digital Communication and local organising committee	As necessary for example following the ASM	As necessary for example following the ASM	Advertisement of the press release on the OHEJP website
Create merchandise and flyers to advertise the OHEJP at events, meetings and workshops	Creative Communication	For each OHEJP event, meeting and workshop. Boxes of merchandise will also be made available for the consortium members	As necessary, for example at the ASM, all WP6 activities, any OHEJP workshops and meetings and when our members represent the OHEJP at external events	Send out merchandise to OHEJP consortium members that would like it

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Draft a CCP mandate to improve the involvement of the OHEJP CCP network	Digital Communication	September 2019	This will be reviewed as necessary	Disseminate the mandate to the CCP network
Encourage the consortium to participate more readily with communications	Communication Team	Ongoing	This will be reviewed as the strategy is implemented to improve communications	Produce a short document stating the communication expectations from the consortium. This will be particularly useful for the new JRPs/JIPS to encourage the correct communication from the start of these projects (needs to be completed by December 2019)
Establish communications with national, European and international contacts to promote the translation of science to policy: Stakeholders Committee Meeting	Communication Team, PMT, WP5	May and November	Twice per year (once in combination with the Annual Scientific Meeting)	Establishment of contacts, publication and dissemination of targeted reports, alignment of OHEJP activities with stakeholders needs, dissemination of results
Create the OHEJP Annual Report	Comms Team, PMT, Project Leaders	Annually in May	Annual	Production and dissemination of an interactive pdf document that is disseminated according to the dissemination policy. The Communication Team is responsible for uploading to the OHEJP website, disseminating on social media and to the CCP network

Communication Expectations from the Consortium

The Communication Team alone, cannot communicate all of the OHEJP news, events and successes, therefore we require input from all members of the consortium. Regular communication with the Communication Team is essential to harmonise the information across the consortium and to ensure that all necessary information is reaching the desired audience through the appropriate channels.

Coordination: The Coordination Team is the first point of contact for any matters relating to the OHEJP, therefore they must keep the Communication Team up to date with any relevant news, events and meetings (PMC, PMC, POC, SSB etc). The Communication Team requires this information as they are responsible for keeping the website and social media platforms up to date. The Communication Team is also in close contact with the CCP network and therefore can effectively disseminate information to the correct target audiences. One social media, information from the OHEJP needs to be consistent, therefore relevant information regarding events and news should be primarily disseminated via the OHEJP platforms. Consortium members are welcome and encouraged to retweet this information and contribute to discussions. Using the OHEJP social media platforms as the primary source of OHEJP information will allow

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the Communication Team to monitor the success and dissemination of OHEJP information. Engagement from consortium members will only improve this success!

The Coordination Team is also responsible to maintaining the consortium spreadsheet which is subsequently sent to the Communication Team for upload to the OHEJP website. The procedure for ensuring this document is up to date is as follows:

- a. The Coordination Team download the most recent version of the consortium spreadsheet from the EJP Consortium Members group on the website.
- b. The Coordination Team update this version of the spreadsheet, highlighting any changes.
- c. The Coordination Team then send the updated version of the spreadsheet to the Communication Team.
- d. The Communication Team checks the file and updates the EJP Consortium Members group, removing the old version of the spreadsheet.

PMT: as the Project Management Team oversee all OHEJP activities, they must contact the Communication Team with any information that should be disseminated via the website, social media or by newsletter. This information must be given to the Communication Team in advance to ensure that messages are effectively conveyed on multiple platforms to multiple audiences.

CCPs: a detailed description of the roles and responsibilities of the CCP network is detailed in Annex1. The CCPs are responsible for communication with the Communication Team with regards to all OHEJP information. The Communication Team will be in regular contact with each CCP and is expected to share information from the Communication Team with their institute.

Project Leaders: the Communication Team will contact the Project Leaders on a quarterly basis to encourage them to contribute to the quarterly Consortium Newsletters. It is the expectation that all Project Leaders will contribute to ensure that each of the JRPs and JIPs is represented. The Project Leaders will also be required to contribute to the OHEJP Annual Report each year to ensure the scientific research is communicated accurately and effectively, this will include validating text and providing images where necessary, It is the responsibility of the Project Leaders to contact the Communication Team regarding new publications, meetings, workshops and events so that they can be put on the website and appropriately advertised. Furthermore, the Project Leaders (or member of the research team) are responsible for uploaded their publications on to Zenodo. The Communication Team curate these publications on Zenodo, and therefore will be notified of the upload and accept accordingly.

All Consortium Members: all members should contact the Communication Team (e.camplimg@surrey.ac.uk) for any OHEJP templates and for the branding guide when creating flyers, documents etc. Please do not hesitate to contact the Communication Team if you have any questions. Additionally, if members are organising events or workshops, they must let the Communication Team know as they can promote the event on the website, on social media and in any upcoming newsletters.

5. Digital Strategy

Website

There are three key objectives of the OHEJP website:

1. To provide a platform to publicly advertise and showcase the work of the OHEJP.
2. To provide a platform where consortium members can communicate and collaborate with other members and track the progress of their projects.
3. To establish the OHEJP brand.

Actions to achieve these objectives:

1. To provide a platform to publicly advertise and showcase the work of the OHEJP. The website is used to promote the OHEJP, to provide information about the project, the consortium, stakeholders, scientific research, education and training activities, news and events. The website successfully provides a platform whereby all OHEJP target audiences can navigate the website to find out more. It is regularly updated to ensure that all information on the front end is up-to-date and engaging. The website is a dynamic platform that is key to the communication strategy of the OHEJP as it has the most influential presence of all platforms detailed in the digital strategy.

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OHEJP Events and Activities:

The front end of the website is used to promote all OHEJP events and WP6 activities. We have a dedicated news and event page which details all OHEJP news and events. These are both OHEJP specific and also related One Health topics that may be of interest to our target audiences. The events, for example are categorised as follows: OHEJP consortium events, OHEJP open events, OHEJP related events and OHEJP invitations. These categories therefore allow our audience to search for events of interest or relevance to themselves. The events are updated regularly by the Communication Team and members can also create their own events that will appear on the front end. The WP6 activities are dedicated to training and education the future generation of One Health scientists, therefore it is important to advertise these effectively on the website to facilitate the creation of a One Health Community. These activities are promoted on their own dedicated pages and all open calls and open applications are advertised on the WP6 home page. A monthly bulletin is also created by the WP6 Project Leader which is available on the website.

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OHEJP News and Updates:

In addition to the content available on the website, the OHEJP consortium and external newsletters are available on the website. The newsletters and social media posts often redirect audiences to the website for more information because it contains more information, presented in an attractive and engaging way.

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OHEJP Scientific Updates and Outcomes:

2. To provide a platform where consortium members can communicate and collaborate with other members and track the progress of their projects

The website also provides a private space where members of the OHEJP consortium can register and access a project management tool which encourages engagement and collaboration across the consortium. The private space has several facilities used by members, including messaging facilities and discussion forums. Members are also able to create and track their deliverables and milestones. In addition, members are able to access a range of key project documents, and able to upload and download a range of file formats from the website securely. There are over 90 groups of on the private space, including but not limited to groups for all OHEJP consortium members, PMT, SSB, Stakeholders, each Work Package, for each of the Joint Research and Joint Integrative Projects and for each of the Education and Training activity calls. These groups are managed by assigned administrators and moderators to promote dialogue and collaboration between members. This is particularly important when participating in the scientific projects and in promoting collaboration in the organisation of events. These groups also create hubs where information can be uploaded and accessed, and organised into smaller projects, thus making it easier for members to find documentation and information.

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In addition to this members' platform, there are a number of other features on the website for members only. These include the facility to add events to the 'News and Events' page and the ability to complete the 'Internal Events Survey' which is essential for the reporting of events and dissemination activities where members present the OHEJP or their work associated with the OHEJP. **Every member that presents the project should complete the survey after the event.**

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3. To establish the OHEJP brand

The OHEJP website was redesigned and rebranded in December 2018 to include the attractive public interface targeted to the previously defined target audiences and the private members' space mentioned above.

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In line with the rebranding, a number of templates including, poster templates, meeting agenda and minutes templates and presentation templates have been created to establish a recognisable brand at events and workshops. Furthermore, there are 'Communication Tools' available on the OHEJP website. The OHEJP also produces a number of newsletters- a quarterly internal newsletter, a bi-annual external newsletter and monthly Education and Training bulletins (WP6 Project Manager's responsibility).

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Going forwards, the focus will be to continue to strengthen the OHEJP presence using the website. This will be achieved by continuing to develop the visual appeal of the public interface of the website, promoting events, improving the content of the website and to increase the traffic to the website from newsletters and the social media platforms.

Monitoring the success of these actions:

Monitoring the success of the digital strategy of the OHEJP website is a key aspect of this digital strategy,

this is essential to sustaining, evaluating and improving upon the communication strategy that has been implemented. The Communication Team have number of KPIs to monitor and improve success.

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Communication of Results and Open Access on website

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Communication of results and open access data are essential components to ensure that the outcomes of the OHEJP are widely disseminated. This effective communication of results ensures that the OHEJP adheres to the FAIR principals (see section 2 of Deliverable 4.4 The OHEJP Data Management Plan (DMP)). The FAIR principles ensure that any data are findable, accessible, inter-operable and usable. Therefore, in addition to using OpenAire/ Zenodo as an open access data repository, public deliverables (both overarching OHEJP deliverables and Project deliverables), publications and any other suitable OHEJP outputs will also be available from the OHEJP website (for example, the publications available for each JRP/JIP are available on the respective project pages. Additionally, there is a link on the ORION page to the ORION Knowledge Hub and Glossary). The website will also link to the OpenAire account to ensure that it is accessible to a wide audience.

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The dissemination of public deliverables is detailed in the 'Dissemination Procedure' which can be found on the [OHEJP Consortium Members Group](#).

The outputs on the OHEJP website will come in several forms:

- a. Public Overarching OHEJP deliverables
- b. Public Project deliverables
- c. Scientific peer reviewed publications
- d. Scientific reports, conference presentations
- e. Data used in publications
- f. Other data gathered in (scientific) projects, but not used in publications.

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Social Media Strategy

The aim of the social media strategy is to increase the visibility of the OHEJP to defined target audiences. This includes: The OHEJP consortium members, OHEJP Governance Bodies (POC, PMC), national mirror groups, European institutions (ECDC; EFA), international organisations (WHO, FAO, OIE), scientists: both internal and external to the consortium in the fields of biological, environmental and social science, students: undergraduates and postgraduates, early career researchers, politicians, stakeholders, professionals: healthcare, farmers, veterinarians, doctors, those in the food industry and the general public.

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The primary platforms to be used in the social media communications strategy are Twitter and LinkedIn. These platforms are managed by the Communication Team (Digital); posts sent from the OHEJP designated social media accounts are validated within the Communication Team at the University of Surrey. In order to improve the efficiency and maximise the use of social media, where possible social media posts will be managed using Hootsuite (<https://hootsuite.com>) a social media management tool which can schedule posts. This ensures that the OHEJP social media accounts will always be active to maintain a strong social media presence, in addition to spreading content over upcoming weeks and months.

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Planning social media content prove particularly useful for promoting internal calls (WP3, WP4 and WP6) and their regular reminders, promoting upcoming workshops and pre-planned OHEJP events. These can be scheduled months in advance. This allows more time for more spontaneous updates and news. Having identified the key audiences for the OHEJP the content for social media posts will be determined by one of the following:

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Communications Aim	Target Audience	How to achieve this aim
<p>Increasing the awareness of the OHEJP and its activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Events organised by OHEJP, JRPs and JIPs Publications Education and Training activities 	<p>OHEJP partners, Scientists, Students, Early Career Researchers, Politicians, Stakeholders (current and potential) Professionals in Europe and beyond, General Public</p>	<p>OHEJP events are extensively advertised on social media. Each event is advertised in advance on Twitter, LinkedIn (this can be achieved using Hootsuite, as mentioned above), on the OHEJP website and in the regular newsletters. Event announcement are also disseminated via email to the consortium and CCPs who forward this information to those of interest within their institute. Similarly, OHEJP publications are presented on the OHEJP website on the individual project pages. A 'Publications' is available to showcase this information. Publications also feature on social media posts and are very popular amongst audiences. These are posted with an image to improve the visibility of the post. Education and Training activities will be advertised regularly on social media and on the website. Save the Date announcements* for all events will be disseminated on social media platforms and via email to raise awareness of each event. Flyers* with all relevant event information will be disseminated similarly. The first OHEJP ASM will be used as a platform to advertise the OHEJP to a wide audience and increase the awareness of annual activities such as summer schools, short term missions etc. with the aim of individual remembering that the OHEJP offers a wide range of opportunities!</p> <p>*The OHEJP Communication Team can provide the branding guide (also available on the OHEJP website) and any OHEJP images. The OHEJP branding must be used for all OHEJP events. The team can also help with the creation of Save the Date announcements and flyers if there is not a local Communications Team employed for an event.</p>
<p>Improving the internal communication of funding calls. This includes WP6 activities, WP4 Integrative Missions etc.</p>	<p>OHEJP internal mailing lists</p>	<p>Funding calls are announced in several different ways. For WP6 there is a monthly bulletin which is sent to the consortium (and any other subscribers) to inform our partners of the funding opportunities and deadlines. This strategy will be monitored by monitoring the success of the newsletter using MailChimp (ie the number of opens and link clicks). The Communication Team and WP6 Project Manager will keep in regular contact regarding this. Furthermore, reminders for calls and deadlines are posted on the website and social media platforms. The WP4 integrative missions have been advertised on social media, on the private space of the website and in the consortium newsletter.</p>
<p>To effectively communicate the scientific outcomes of the OHEJP.</p>	<p>OHEJP Partners Stakeholders PMC, POC, SSB Wider Scientific Community</p>	<p>The scientific outcomes of the JRPs/JIPs are regularly updated on the OHEJP website (on the publications page and the individual project pages). Additionally, the publications are available on the OpenAire/Zenodo platform which can be accessed from the OHEJP website. Publications are also celebrated in the Consortium Newsletter, which is sent to mailing lists including the PMC, POC and SSB. Twitter and LinkedIn are also used to disseminate the publications because this can reach wide audiences, in addition any contributing researchers and institutes can be tagged to increase the dissemination.</p>

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Disseminate key website information	OHEJP Partners and Researchers	The website is constantly being updated and new information is being added. Website pages are shared on social media and key information is shared in the Consortium Newsletter. Furthermore, if significant changes are made to website pages, for example the Project pages being update or PhD pages being created, the relevant Project Leaders or Principle Investigators will be made aware. This ensures that the appropriate audiences are aware of any changes, and also encourages them to provide any updated information for the page.
Disseminating key internal OHEJP updates	OHEJP Partners	When appropriate, emails are sent to the consortium with important information. To minimise the number of emails sent, if information is not urgent, it will appear in the Consortium Newsletter.
Topical news articles such as AMR, FBZ and ET news, policy change, national press releases or documentation	OHEJP partners, Scientists, Students, Early Career Researchers, Professionals, General Public	Research for social media posts is always ongoing to ensure that (where possible) topical news articles, documents etc. are read and reported on. Many articles such as those from key stakeholders such as EFSA and ECDC are posted on the OHEJP social media accounts and are well received by followers. Topics relating to One Health, Antimicrobial Resistance, Foodborne Zoonoses and Emerging Threats are preferred content, however other external topics such as climate change are also considered. Much of the OHEJP social media feeds are populated with content from topical articles.
Increasing awareness of related events such as One Health conferences	OHEJP partners, Scientists, Students, Early Career Researchers, NRL partners, Ministries (PH, Agri, Res), Food /environmental agencies	Other news and events relating to One Health are posted on social media platforms because they could potentially be of interest to the OHEJP followers. Furthermore, members of PMT are often invited to speak at such events to showcase the OHEJP. Increasing awareness by using social media and by posting these events on the 'Events' section of the website will ensure individual engage with the OHEJP for other One Health related events and that the website can be the 'go to' for One Health events.
Engaging with the general public such as increasing the understanding of AMR, FBZ and ET	General Public	The OHEJP will use infographics containing facts, graphs and statistics in a manageable format that would be engaging for a public audience. The use of simple language in all social media posts and external newsletters will help maintain engagement and interest with the content provided. The OHEJP will also offer a Communication and Media Workshop in 2020 to consortium members which will teach essential communication skills.

Strategy for individual social media platforms
Twitter: @OneHealthEJP

Twitter is a 'fast-paced' social media platform that requires a high level of engagement to ensure that the number of followers, impressions and engagements continues to increase. Furthermore, it has a high level of engagement from the scientific community, important stakeholders and the general public, to name a few. Twitter enables the OHEJP to connect with partner institutes and researches by tagging them in relevant information or sharing their news, events or publications. This helps to highlight the collaborations within the OHEJP and more effectively disseminate information from a multitude of institutes and research projects. Additionally, key OHEJP stakeholders such as EFSA, ECDC, COMPARE, EU-JAMRAI and JPI AMR are very active on Twitter which enables the Communication Team to tag them in relevant posts, share relevant information and encourage the reciprocal sharing of information. For example, the CO is in regular contact with the Communication Team at EU-JAMRAI who often tag the OHEJP in their social media campaigns and share OHEJP news and events. This improves dissemination of information to wider audiences.

Twitter Conversations:

Twitter is important for the OHEJP Communications Strategy because it allows the OHEJP to be involved in social media conversations. To achieve this, relevant hashtags need to be identified to contribute to these conversations and interact with the desired target audiences, as detailed in above. Relevant hashtags for the OHEJP key research domains, antimicrobial resistance, foodborne zoonoses and emerging threats have been identified in the table below.

OHEJP Domain		
Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)	Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ)	Emerging Threats (ET)
#AMR	#FoodborneZoonoses	#EmergingThreats
#AntimicrobialResistance	#Zoonoses	#InfectiousDisease
#AntimicrobialStewardship	#FoodSafety	Other specific diseases
#Infection	#Food	
#Research	#Health	
#Science	#PublicHealth	
#KeepAntibioticsWorking	#Salmonella	
#Microbiology	#Ecoli	
#Medicine	#Listeria	
#Health	#SafeFood	
#Bacteria	#FoodPoisoning	
#Antibiotics	Other specific bacteria	
#Superbugs		
#Resistance		

Engaging with a wider audience:

In addition to the key research domains (FBZ, AMR and ET), the OHEJP also recognises other related topics, such as 'One Health', 'Research' and related events. The 'One Health' community on Twitter is growing rapidly as use of this term grows. This has been fuelled by the EU-JAMRAI campaign to improve the use of the One Health hashtag following their social media listening initiative.

Furthermore, there is a community of PhD students that can be targeted using the #PhDchat and also a community of Early Career Researchers that can be targeted using the #ECRchat. This will prove useful for advertising the OHEJP Education and Training activities and the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting for the duration of the OHEJP. Key hashtags are shown in the table below.

Engaging with Events:

It is also important to engage with special events relating to the OHEJP or the key domains of the OHEJP, these events often have their own hashtags with their own conversations. For example, World Antibiotic Awareness Week (#WAAW) initiated by the WHO, European Antibiotic Awareness Day (#EAAD #EAAD19) initiated by ECDC and One Health Day (#OneHealthDay) initiated by the One Health Platform and the One Health Commission.

Engaging with these hashtags will highlight the OHEJP involvement in key activities relating to research aims and also increases the presence of the OHEJP in front of a captive audience. Therefore, engagement with these events requires communication with the organisers, planning and quality content to showcase the OHEJP effectively.

It is also important to generate hashtags for key OHEJP event such as the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting (#OHEJPASM2019 #OHEJPASM2020 #OHEJPASM2021 #OHEJPASM2022). This will encourage delegates to have conversations on Twitter, share content from the event and raise the profile of the event. Furthermore, these hashtags act as an archive for information from previous events which can be referred back to or shared again.

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Other OHEJP Related Topics		
One Health	Research	Events
#OneHealthEJP	#H2020	#OHEJPASM2019
#OneHealth	#ResearchImpactEU	#AntibioticAwarenessWeek
#OneHealth4All	#Collaboration	#WAAW (2019)
#HealthForAll	#Intergration	#EAAW
#Environment	#PhDchat	#Pint19
#EnvironmentalHealth	#ECRchat	#OHEJPsummerSchool19
#Veterinary	#Europe	#OneHealthDay
#Livestock	#OneHealthCommunity	
#Farmers		
#Vets		
#Animals		
#PublicHealth		
#FoodSafety		
#EpiTwitter		

OHEJP Projects:

Each of the OHEJP Joint Research and Joint Integrative projects have their own hashtag for use on social media. This is to allow the updates from each project to be tracked on social media feeds. This could prove particularly useful for the project leaders and researchers who would like to showcase their project online. This also enables the Communication Team to monitor these hashtags and share information if the OHEJP account was not tagged in a post. These hashtags also feature on the individual project pages on the OHEJP website (shown in the table below).

There are a number of Joint Research and Joint Integrative projects whose project leaders and scientific researchers engage with the OHEJP, on Twitter especially. We to encourage as many members as possible to use Twitter to share their work, updates and events and to engage with the OHEJP. This exemplifies the integrative and collaborative nature of the OHEJP, increases its visibility on social media platforms and works towards the aim to create a One Health Community.

OHEJP Project	Hashtag
One health surveillance Initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation	#ORION
One Health Structures in Europe	#COHESIVE
Improving phenotypic Antimicrobial Resistance Testing by development of sensitive screening assays for emerging resistances, and setting missing ECOFFs	#IMPART
Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment	#ARDIG
Risk and Disease burden of Antimicrobial Resistance	#RaDAR
Metagenomic Array Detection of emerging Virus in EU	#MADVIR
Development and harmonisation of innovative methods for comprehensive analysis of foodborne toxigenic bacteria, i.e. <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> and <i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	#TOXdetect

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Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain	#NOVA
Adaptive traits of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> to its diverse ecological niches	#LISTADAPT
Standardisation and validation of metagenomics methods for the detection of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats	#METASTAVA
Air-sampling, A Low-Cost Screening Tool in Biosecured Broiler Production	#AIRSAMPLE
Monitoring the gut microbiota and immune response to predict, prevent and control zoonoses in humans and livestock in order to minimise the use of antimicrobials	#MoMIR
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> : from ecology to source attribution and transmission control	#MedVetKlebs
Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union	#CARE
One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants	#HARMONYCAP
Connecting dimensions in One-Health surveillance	#MATRIX
Discovering the sources of <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , VTEC and antimicrobial resistance	#DISCOVER
Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe	#BIOPIGEE
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> sources quantified	#TOXOSOURCES
Assessing Determinants of the Non-Decreasing Incidence of <i>Salmonella</i>	#ADONIS
Building Integrative Tools for One Health Surveillance	#BEONE
Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests	#FARMED
Full-length sequencing for an enhanced EFFORT to map and understand drivers and reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance	#FULLFORCE
Development of new tools for real-time detection of zoonotic bacteria and antimicrobial resistance in veterinary, human and environmental sources	#WORLDCOM
The role of free extracellular DNA in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain	#FEDAMR
Point-of-incidence toolbox for emerging virus threats	#TELEVIR
Multi-centre study on <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> and <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> s.l. in Europe: development and harmonisation of diagnostic methods in the food chain	#MEME
Parasite Detection, Isolation and Evaluation	#PARADISE
Identification of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species: new threats for human and animals	#IDEMBRU

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OHEJP Project	Hashtag
From genotype to phenotype: patho-evolution of <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> French strains	#PeMbo
Investigation of the molecular basis, origin, transferability and risk factors associated with linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin	#LINRES
Environment and Diseases: A general method linking Mechanism and Phenomenology	#EnvDis
Dynamics of <i>E.coli</i> in laying hens	#ECOHEN
Development of an aptamer-based test for <i>Trichinella</i> detection	#AptaTrich
Study of the tropism and persistence of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> : from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative microbiological risk assessment	#ToxSauQMRA
Tracking bacterial pathogens through sources, geography and time using stable phylogenetically informative genome codes	#Codes4strains
<i>In vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> analyses and modulation of the chicken gut microbiome to combat AMR	#VIMOGUT
Mathematical models and economic evaluation for cystic echinococcosis control and elimination	#MACE
Contribution of wild birds to AMR in the environment and on farms	#WILBR
Investigating the role of heavy metals in the environment as a selective pressure for the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance	#HMEAMR
Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant <i>Salmonella</i> Kentucky ST198	#KENTUCKY
Tracking the public health hazard of foodborne Hepatitis E	#TRACE
Metagenomics and genomic approaches for the prevention of the spread of plazomicin resistance in humans, animals and the environment	#METAPRO
Developing evidence-based surveillance for emerging rat-borne zoonoses in changing environments	#DESIRE
Understanding the development of fluoroquinolone (FQ) resistance in <i>Campylobacter</i> present in broilers and the risks of FQ resistance persisting through the food-chain to cause disease in people	#UDoFRiC

OHEJP PhD Projects:

The OHEJP has funded a total of sixteen PhD projects. Work Package 6 will liaise with the PhD supervisors and PhD students to create hashtags for each of these projects and encourage the supervisors and students to actively engage in Twitter and post appropriate updates from their projects.

Social media content will be determined by the PhD supervisor and PhD student; however, they should follow these guidelines when using Twitter to share their research and progress:

- All posts should use the hashtag #OneHealthEJP and the designated project hashtag
- All posts should tag @OneHealthEJP so that the Communication Team can share the post
- Posts should not contain sensitive information regarding the project
- Examples of content to share include publications, collaborative work (for example if the

-
- e. student had used a OHEJP STM to learn a new skill), non-sensitive updates
This work can also be shared with the PhD community by using the hashtags #PhD #PhDlife #PhDchat. These are well known PhD communities on Twitter.

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A group on the private space of the website will be set up by the WP6 Project Manager as a line of communication with PhD PIs. This group will contain all relevant documents, downloadable logos, image etc. Project logos for each of the PhD projects are also available and have already been provided to the PhD supervisors.

Key Influencers on Twitter:

Tagging influential bodies in the OHEJP tweets will help to increase the impressions of the tweets and highlights the collaborative nature of the OHEJP. For example, tagging our stakeholders EFSA and ECDC and highlighting them as key stakeholders; EFSA and ECDC have 28,000 and 25,000 followers, respectively and therefore if they retweet our tweets, the number of impressions is greatly increased. Furthermore, the Communication Team works closely with the Communication Team at EU-JAMRAI whereby we tag each other in tweets to broaden each other's' impact to different audiences. Other potential stakeholders such as the WHO, FAO and OIE are also active on Twitter, interacting with their content and tagging them in posts could encourage retweets to their network.

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The recent collaboration with the One Health Platform and One Health Commission will also aid in the promotion of the OHEJP content. Tagging each in posts may increase the OHEJP audience if the posts are retweeted.

Similarly, it is important to engage with the OHEJP partner institutes on Twitter, this highlights the collaborative and integrative nature of the project and also increases the audience for the OHEJP tweets. This will be achieved by tagging our partner institutes in posts (this has been successful for the OHEJP Summer School) and retweeting their work, especially if it is linked to the OHEJP.

Interacting with Consortium Members on Twitter:

Currently, the OHEJP interacts with consortium members on Twitter, however we would like to encourage more activity from our members. Therefore, members with Twitter accounts are encouraged to follow the OHEJP Twitter account. The OHEJP social media accounts are highlighted at all meetings (ie SSB, PMC, POC etc) to encourage activity from consortium members. They are also highlighted at all OHEJP events. Furthermore, when posting OHEJP related content they are encouraged to tag @OneHealthEJP and also use the hashtag #OneHealthEJP. The OHEJP Twitter account can then share these posts, thus highlighting the activity across the consortium and demonstrating the collaborative and integrative nature of our consortium. Increased activity from our members shows that the OHEJP is an active and dynamic consortium and also allows the OHEJP to have a greater reach on social media.

Monitoring the success of the Twitter strategy:

This strategy is being monitored with a series of KPIs to monitor and improve the success of the Twitter strategy.

LinkedIn:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2020-one-health-ejp>

LinkedIn has a different audience to that of Twitter. LinkedIn is a social media platform that is most frequently used by over 65 million professionals, businesses and institutes. Therefore, content targeted towards the general public will be used less frequently on this platform.

Similar strategies of posting content on LinkedIn have been adopted to that of the Twitter strategies. Similar hashtags are used, and companies are tagged in posts as frequently as possible to increase the engagement throughout the consortium.

LinkedIn is primarily used for professional networking, therefore, posting OHEJP updates and adverts for workshops and training would appeal to the audiences on this social media platform. For example, the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2019 and Summer School 2019 were extensively advertised on LinkedIn and has gained interest from professionals and institutes interested in this event, more so than on Twitter. Some institutes are more active on LinkedIn compared to Twitter, for example Teagasc. LinkedIn has also been a successful platform to promote events such as the ASM Satellite Workshop 2019 and has resulted in registrations to the event.

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In order to monitor the success of event advertisement on the different social media platforms, each event registration form must have the final question 'How did you hear about this event?'. The options listed must include OHEJP website, Twitter, LinkedIn and any other additional platform used. The anonymous answers to the questions must be sent to the Communication Team. This will facilitate the evaluation of the different platforms as means to advertise different events.

Monitoring the success of the LinkedIn strategy

This strategy is being monitored with a series of KPIs to monitor and improve the success of the LinkedIn strategy.

Other Social Media Platforms:

Platforms such as Instagram have been discussed to create a platform for students attending Short Term Missions (STMs), the OHEJP Summer School and the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting. This could be effectively used to promote work and travel, in addition to creating a OHEJP Alumni community. Using the 'stories' function on Instagram would encourage students to engage with the OHEJP. Students could also be encouraged to take over the account for a week to promote a project they are working on or a STM that they are undertaking. In addition to facilitating student interactions, this could target research groups within the OHEJP to strengthen the involvement of the research project teams and also the relationships between project leaders and WP leaders. This may be trialled in 2020 if there is enough interest from the consortium to participate.

Although the OHEJP does not have a Facebook profile, advertising the OHEJP events through the One Health Commission's Facebook page will be a useful tool to increase the advertisement of OHEJP events. This work particularly well when advertising the 2019 OHEJP Summer School because the One Health Commission has a well-established, large, global One Health network that was interested in the Summer School programme. This facility will be used for future Summer Schools and future events, such as workshops that are open to a global audience. Currently, utilising established platforms on Facebook is a more effective use of Facebook than beginning to create a new OHEJP network.

Strategy for OHEJP Internal Calls:

There are a number of internal calls that will be launched throughout the duration of the OHEJP. The remaining calls are for Work Package 6 Education and Training activities; therefore, the Communication Team and WorkPackage 6 Project Manager have developed a strategy to ensure that these internal calls are well advertised on the website, social media and within the consortium. Although this content only applies to audiences within the OHEJP Consortium, it is advantageous to include this content on social media as a number of members have social media accounts therefore this would act as a reminder of calls and deadlines. Furthermore, it shows the wider audience that the OHEJP has a number of ongoing activities and that we are a very active consortium.

The communication of WP6 internal calls will be primarily through a WP6 monthly bulletin which will contain information about current funding opportunities, approaching deadlines, application information to apply to organise and attend WP activities, approaching deadlines and any other WP6 news. This bulletin ensures that all of the WP6 information is in one easy to read email and avoids a high volume of emails from the WP6 Project Manager. For each of the WP6 activities, a group for those interested in the call to organise each event will be created for members to join. In these groups, reminders will be posted on the news feed to remind members of upcoming deadlines. These will be posted one month, two weeks and one week before the deadline.

**Work Package 6 Monthly Bulletin
Accountability and Content: WP6 Project Manager (Piyali Basu)**

The WP6 Project Manager uses Mailchimp to disseminate the WP6 Education and Training activities through a bulletin at the start of every month.

The aim of this bulletin is to provide an update on the events already organised and taking place in the current year, and to provide up-to date information regarding the calls to organise the training events and participate in the education activities the following year.

The bulletin is sent to the following mailing lists:

- Project Management Team
- Scientific Steering Board (Institutes Representatives and Scientific Representatives)
- Programme Managers Committee

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- Coordination Team
- Support Team
- Communication Contact Persons
- Project Leaders
- Additional consortium members who have joined the mailing list.

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The Twitter and LinkedIn accounts are used to promote this bulletin to the members of the consortium that have social media accounts and are following the OHEJP official channels.

The consortium is encouraged to forward this bulletin within their institute to those they think would be interested. The following statement should be included at the top of the bulletin: *“Please forward this bulletin to those within your institute who may be interested. This email has been disseminated to OHEJP institute representatives, scientific representatives, communication contact points, project leaders, Programme Managers Committee and the Project Management Team”.*

The bulletin is designed to highlight the funding opportunities at the top of the email to attract a greater audience to the WP6 internal calls and any key announcements e.g. extension of deadlines, countdown to deadline etc.

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MailChimp has a number of useful analytics channels that are essential for monitoring the success and dissemination of these bulletins. MailChimp has also been integrated into the Google Analytics for the OHEJP website, therefore the traffic to the website from the bulletins is monitored regularly. The use of MailChimp allows the number of people that have opened the newsletter to be monitored, along with which links are the most popular, in addition to identifying who is forwarding these emails.

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Consortium Newsletter

All OHEJP Newsletters will be created using MailChimp. MailChimp has a number of useful analytics channels that are essential for monitoring the success and dissemination of the OHEJP newsletters. MailChimp has also been integrated into the Google Analytics for the OHEJP website, therefore the traffic to the website from the newsletters is monitored regularly. The use of MailChimp allows the number of people that have opened the newsletter to be monitored, in addition to identifying who is forwarding these emails.

- **Accountability:** Digital Communications (Jade Passey) is responsible for creating and distributing of the newsletters using the content provided to them.
- **Content:** The internal newsletter will include key announcements, updates on JRPs and JIPs, project meetings, deliverables, news-worthy updates from the OHEJP partner institutes, the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) and other upcoming events organised by OHEJP partners.

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The content type and length required will be specified by the Communication Team. Content will be provided by the following methods:

- Jade Passey will contact CCPs monthly for institute updates
- Jade Passey will contact PMT, Coordination Team, WP leaders, Project Leaders on a monthly basis for updates
- Outside of the monthly communications, spontaneous communication is encouraged from any member of the consortium (we already have many members doing this). The relevant members of the consortium are expected to contact the Communication Team directly in advance with content (text and appropriate images) for any unplanned activities.

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- **Length:** The newsletter should aim to be two pages on average.
- **Frequency:** The newsletter will be published every three months.
- **Validation:** The final draft the newsletter will be sent to the Communication Team at Surrey and then PMT for validation at least 7 days before deadline. Final validation must be completed at least 48 hours before publication date.
- **Target audience:** The Consortium Newsletter is targeted to internal audiences primarily, however, will not contain any confidential information. The internal mailing lists that the Consortium Newsletter will be sent to are as follows: Programme Managers Committee, Programme Owners Committee, Scientific Steering Board, Project Management Team and the Support Team (as per the figure below), in addition to Project Leaders, Communication Contact Persons, Stakeholders

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and active Third-Party members. All consortium members are encouraged to forward newsletters to anyone that may be interested in updates from the OHEJP. The Communication Team will also forward all newsletters to the CCP network who are expected to forward this within their institutes to anyone that may be interested. Although the primary audience for these newsletters is internal, these newsletters will be uploaded on to the OHEJP website by the Communication Team and published on social media platforms. This will increase the visibility of the OHEJP to external audiences, especially other members of the scientific community that may be interested in collaborating with the OHEJP.

- **Promotion:** the consortium newsletter is uploaded on to the 'Newsletters' page of the OHEJP website and is also advertised on the social media platforms. Furthermore, a link to each consortium newsletter is posed on the newsfeed of the 'OHEJP Consortium' group on the private space of the website.
- **Measuring success:** MailChimp tracks the number of opens, bounces and forwards. It also tracks the number of link clicks and because it has been linked with the Google Analytics account, it can track the traffic directed to the website. The analytics from MailChimp and Google Analytics will be used to measure the success of each newsletter.

External Newsletter

Similarly, to the Consortium Newsletter, the External Newsletter will be created using MailChimp to monitor the success and dissemination of the newsletter. The External Newsletter sign up feature on the website directly links to the OHEJP MailChimp account therefore the number of 'opens' and 'links clicked' will be carefully monitored for the external mailing list to ensure that subscribers are reading and interacting with the newsletter they signed up to. If this is not the case, the communication strategy for the external newsletter will need to be altered. This will be closely monitored when the next External Newsletter is published in June 2019.

The content of the External Newsletter will be targets primarily to a wider audience. Therefore, will contain more images, be more interactive and use simplified language in order to appeal to a wide range of people with scientific and non-scientific backgrounds. This newsletter will contain short pieces of information which will link to additional information, should the reader wish to read more. This will help to maintain interested and will not appear overwhelming when it reaches the subscribers inbox.

- **Accountability:** Digital Communications (Jade Passey) is responsible for creating and distributing of the external newsletters.
- **Content:** The external newsletter will include non-sensitive information which is newsworthy for the wider public. The content of this newsletter will be based on the two internal newsletters previous to publication. Examples of content include project updates, deliverables, updates from the OHEJP partner institutes, the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) and other 'open' upcoming events organised by OHEJP partners.
- **Length:** The newsletter should aim to be a maximum of four pages.
- **Frequency:** The newsletter will be published every six months. The first newsletter was published in December 2018.
- **Validation:** The final draft the newsletter will be send to the Communication Team at Surrey and then PMT for validation at least 7 days before deadline. Final validation must be completed at least 48 hours before publication date.
- **Target audience: The external newsletter is mainly targeted towards the wider general public.** The external newsletter will be sent to the following governance bodies: PMT, Institute Representatives, Scientific Representative, Programme Owner Representatives, Finance, Admin, Project leaders, CCPs, Stakeholders, active Third-Party members, Programme Managers Committee, and finally any individual who has registered to be part of the mailing list for our external newsletter through the website.
- **Promotion:** This newsletter will be uploaded on the 'Newsletters' page of our OHEJP website for the wider public and will also be communicated via the OHEJP social media channels and will be sent via email encouraging circulation within the partner institutes (not restricting to those who belong to the consortium).
- **Measuring success:** MailChimp tracks the number of opens, bounces and forwards. It also tracks the number of link clicks and because it has been linked with the Google Analytics account, it can track the traffic directed to the website. The analytics from MailChimp and Google Analytics will be used to measure the success of each newsletter.

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OHEJP Annual Report for Stakeholders

Each year, it is the responsibility of the CO to produce an annual report for the OHEJP. This report is a OHEJP deliverable and will be an update of the successes each year until the end of the programme in 2022.

- **Accountability:** the Communication Team is responsible for creating this document.
- **Content:** The content for this report will be determined by the Summary Progress Report and the 9- and 12-month reports from the JRP and JIPs. It is the responsibility of Coordination and the Support Team to ensure that the Communication Team has access to all of these documents 2 months before the annual report is due.
- **Length:** the report will be kept to the minimum possible.
- **Validation:** the Communication Team will create the content for the report and validate each section with the relevant WP Leaders and Project Leaders. The final compiled content will then be sent to PMT for validation, two weeks will be given for this feedback.
- **Target Audience:** this document will be written for all audiences, both internal and external to the consortium. It will be of particular interest to stakeholders (WP5 responsibility) and the public (Communication Team responsibility).
- **Promotion:** The document will be disseminated in accordance to the Dissemination Strategy detailed above.
- **Measuring Success:** in terms of the digital strategy, the number of link clicks will be monitored on Google Analytics, Twitter and LinkedIn.

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Press Releases

Press releases should be released for any OHEJP event or any OHEJP related news of public interest. These press releases are the responsibility of the institute hosting the event or reporting any news. The hosting institute must contact the Communication Team to make them aware off any press release so that this can also be shared on the OHEJP website and social media platforms.

As part of the overall Communications Strategy, the Communication Team will contact the CCPs on a monthly basis regarding information from each institute which may include press releases. As previously mentioned, CCPs are also encouraged to contact the Communication Team with any additional information outside of the monthly communication email. The CCPs can request press release information from within their institute in a way they deem appropriate and communicate this with the Communication Team. The content will be validated within the Communication Team at Surrey initially, followed by PMT. Therefore, it is essential that information is received by the Communication Team 10 working days before the proposed date of release.

OHEJP ASM Press Releases

There will be a press release following each OHEJP ASM; this will be the responsibility of the organising institute(s). The Communication Team can help with this press release where appropriate or requested. Following the publication of this press release, the organising institute must contact the Communication Team so that the article can be disseminated on the OHEJP website and in the subsequent newsletter after the ASM.

The press release from the first ASM is now available on the OHEJP website.

Press releases will be promoted on the OHEJP website and on social media, in order to reach a wide audience. It will also be important to disseminate this information within the consortium. This will be achieved by posting updates on the OHEJP Consortium group on the private space of the website and including any press release in consortium newsletters.

Short Scientific Article

The Communication Team is responsible for the organisation of the One Health short article. This article will be an opinion piece for journals such as the *Vet Record* and or the *British Medical Journal* and will be written in collaboration with the WP6 team and the OHEJP researchers at the University of Surrey and

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should be no longer than two pages. This article will describe the history of the concept of One Health, the OHEJP definition of One Health, the areas to date that One Health has focused on, and how OHEJP will use a more collaborative and integrative approach to impact the One Health field.

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Special issue on OH Zoonoses for a scientific journal

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At the end of the OHEJP, the Communication Team will seek to have a special issue on One Health Zoonoses in a relevant scientific journal (e.g. Journal of Medical Microbiology One Health section, EcoHealth) to capture the four main themes of the EJP. The Communication Team is responsible for coordinating the production of this article, but the content will be provided by all WP Leaders, Deputy Leaders, PIs etc. This will be validated and edited by the Project Management Team.

This will be promoted by communication methods which are still available after the duration of the project. This issue will be promoted both via internal communication methods (website private space communication functionalities) and external communication methods (public face of website, Twitter, LinkedIn, external newsletter etc.). More details will follow.

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OHEJP Communication Tools

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[Flyer \(external\)](#)

A validated branded flyer was created which is intended for wide distribution at a wide range of events to advertise the Project. The flyer is a two-page document that succinctly showcases the OHEJP. It highlights the key messages and activities of the OHEJP in an attractive design which is targeted for all audiences, including the general public. This flyer emphasises that the OHEJP is a five-year project, that it is Horizon 2020 funded (total €90 million) and that the consortium is composed of 44 partners from across Europe. This document also highlights the activities of the OHEJP: Joint Research and Joint Integrative Projects, ASM, Summer Schools, Doctoral Programme and the CPD module. Additionally, it contains all of the information of the OHEJP social media accounts, hashtags, website address and the OHEJP QR code which links to the website. The back of the flyer contains quote from Project Coordinator (Arnaud Callegari) and Scientific Coordinator (Hein Imberechts).

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This flyer will be printed and disseminated at OHEJP events and should also be available in the partner institutes for example in waiting areas and leaflet racks. The flyer is also periodically shared on the OHEJP social media networks.

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[Brief \(external\)](#)

Available on the OHEJP website: Outcomes > Communication tools.

A one-page branded brief has been validated to introduce the OHEJP briefly describing the main objectives, the key activities that will be carried out, the impact of the research and activities, and management of sustainability. This can be used to provide a summary of the project when advocating about the project.

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[OHEJP Poster \(external\)](#)

Available on the OHEJP website (private space) 'OHEJP Consortium members' group.

A validated OHEJP poster is available in the consortium members group of the OHEJP website. This poster can be used when describing and presenting the OHEJP. This has been disseminated to the consortium via the private space and is also available on request from members. When documents are uploaded on to the private space, member of the group are notified by email so all members will be aware that this document is available.

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[Work Package 6 Poster \(external\)](#)

This poster can be used by the WP6 team, the Coordination Team and the PMT when hosting a OHEJP event. The Communication Team can provide this to the above team members upon request.

[PowerPoint Presentation \(external\)](#)

Available on the OHEJP website (private space) 'OHEJP Consortium members' group.

A validated OHEJP PowerPoint presentation is available in the consortium members group of the OHEJP website. This presentation can be used when presenting the OHEJP at conferences, meetings and events. This has been disseminated to the consortium via the private space and is also available on request from members. When documents are uploaded on to the private space, member of the group are notified by email so all members will be aware that this document is available.

Templates (internal)

Available in the OHEJP Consortium Members group on the OHEJP website private space: [Dissemination Information Pack](#)

- [Minutes of the meeting](#)
- [Agenda](#)
- [Deliverable](#)
- [Attendance list](#)
- [Scientific poster](#)

- A validated OHEJP poster is available on the private space of the website. This should be used for all OHEJP poster presentations at conferences, events and meetings. This poster template has been disseminated to all Project Leaders to forward on to their researchers and any consortium members who may find it useful.

8. General Data Protection Regulation

- The OHEJP website has GDPR functionality built into it, which allows members to request and download their data. The OHEJP [privacy policy and cookie policy](#) can be found on the website.

- OHEJP will keep the electronic and paper records of applications and scoresheets for the successful short-term missions (STMs), PhDs, workshops (WS), summer schools, continuing professional development (CPD) module for a maximum period of 24 months after the decision.

- We will destroy the records (both paper and electronic) of all unsuccessful STM, WS, summer schools, CPD and PhD applications by 12 months after the decision.

- The expert reviewers will delete all records associated with PhD, STM and WS reviews after 12 months whether or not the application was successful (we have a responsibility to see that data we have transmitted to third parties is also deleted).

- Permission will be requested from successful STM and WS applicants to keep their website reports available on the website.

- The GB, Institute representatives and deputies, and scientific committee will be requested to provide explicit consent for the OHEJP to hold their email addresses, work positions and addresses, and to be able to contact them about any matters relevant to the activities of the OHEJP.

- The Project effectively constitute the 'Controller' who must only hold and process data absolutely necessary for the completion of their duties in the interests of 'data minimisation'. Access to the data will be limited to those who would otherwise not be able to carry out their duties. It will not be possible to conduct the necessary activities of the OHEJP without keeping records of your contact details. You may request sight of the data we hold on you at any time. Similarly, you may withdraw your consent at any time and we will delete your records.

- For marketing purposes, the Communications Team will record, reproduce, and use the images and/or voice recordings taken during audio, video and photographic capture throughout the duration of the One Health EJP project. Written consent gained via the event registration process or the "Authorisation for the recording and use of participant images" form will be sent to individuals prior to any event.

Annex 1: One Health EJP Communication Contact Person (CCP) Mandate

This document details the roles and responsibilities of the One Health EJP (OHEJP) Communication Contact Person (CCP). The CCP network is composed of a nominated person at each of the institutes in the OHEJP consortium.

The overarching role for the CCP is to work with the OHEJP Communications Team to facilitate and improve communication across the consortium. The Communication Team resides at the University of Surrey, UK and currently consists of the Project Manager (PM), Piyali Basu and the Digital Communication Officer (DCO), Jade Passey and the Creative Communications Officer (CCO), Elaine Campling. The CCP network will work closely with the DCO.

The CCP network was created to enhance communication across the consortium and to ensure that news, events and information would be disseminated across all institutes and that this information is received by the correct people. For example, that events across the OHEJP consortium reach the researchers and collaborators of our partner institutes or that information regarding global events that may be of interest to our consortium reaches the correct individuals.

Each CCP is encouraged to register to the OHEJP website: onehealthjep.eu and join the CCP group where updates and information will be shared. Furthermore, we encourage CCPs to engage with our social media networks. We currently use [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

The key roles of each CCP are:

1. To disseminate information received from the DCO to their institute
 - a. This may be in the form of the Internal (quarterly) newsletter, External (biannual) newsletter, Education and Training activities Bulletin, emails, events etc.
2. To have regular communication with the DCO and keep them informed of any news, events and publications within their institute which may be of interest of the One Health EJP consortium.
3. To adhere to the Communication Strategy written by the Communication Team and promote awareness of the Communication Strategy to those involved in the OHEJP within their institute.
4. To follow-up on necessary emails from the DCO and adhere to agreed deadlines. When forwarding on information provided by the DCO, please copy in the Communications mailbox (OHEJPcommunications@surrey.ac.uk) so that the team can track dissemination.
5. To inform the DCO and Support Team (ohjepcoord@anses.fr) if they no longer wish to continue in the role of CCP or let the DCO know if a new CCP has been nominated for their institute.
6. To take initiative to collaborate with other members of the OHEJP and other CCPs in relevant communication activities.

In order to facilitate this, the key roles of the DCO within the CCP network are:

1. To communicate on a regular basis with the CCPs.
2. To organise an annual meeting with the CCPs at the University of Surrey.
3. To provide the CCPs with up to date information regarding OHEJP events, news, publications etc.
4. To support the CCPs in their role.

For more information on the CCP Mandate please do not hesitate to contact Jade Passey jade.passey@surrey.ac.uk

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- WP2 INTEGRATIVE STRATEGIC RESEARCH AGENDA
- WP3 MANAGEMENT OF JOINT RESEARCH PROJECTS
- WP4 MANAGEMENT OF JOINT INTEGRATIVE PROJECTS

Responsible Partner: ANSES
Contributing Partners: BfR, INSA, IP, ISS, NVI, RIVM, SCIENSANO, SSI, UCM, UoS, WbvR

Version: 2 / Issue Date: June 2021

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DISSEMINATION PROCEDURE

This document describes the **flow of outputs** (i.e. One Health EJP deliverables, JRP, JIP and PhD deliverables and publications) **during their drafting and finalisation**, with the aim of making them publicly available (**Open Access**). The specific actions for WP Leaders, Project Leaders, and their respective collaborators, in addition to the Communication Team (Comms Team) and Support Team (ST), are described in this step by step procedure.

This document does not cover explicitly the dissemination efforts some One Health EJP WP and the Communications Team make to convey most relevant outcome to targeted stakeholders, with the objective to increase impact.

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Key Contact Information

Communications Team:
ohajpcommunications@surrey.ac.uk

Support Team:
ohajpcoord@anses.fr
ohajp@sciensano.be

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OHEJP Work Package Deliverables

Responsibility: Work Package Leaders (PMT)

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1. The ST follows up the submission dates of deliverables and sends reminders to the One Health EJP WP Leaders 30 to 45 days before the submission deadline. The submission dates are a recurrent item addressed at the Coordination Team regular conference calls or meetings.

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2. The One Health EJP WP Leader who is responsible for drafting a new One Health EJP deliverable, uploads the nearly final version to the Sciensano SharePoint ([Documents for validation by PMT](#)).

3. The author of the deliverable sends an email to all PMT members (with the PMT collaborators, ST and the Comms Team in the cc) to inform the upload on SharePoint. The PMT members and PMT collaborators can therefore suggest modifications, monitor strategic developments (WP2) and identify information relevant for stakeholders (WP5) or for sustainability plans (WP7). PMT members may comment on the suggested beneficiaries and inform the Comms Team.

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4. The PMT validates the document, preferably within 1 to 2 weeks. The One Health EJP WP Leader informs the ST, which puts it on the participant portal of the European Commission (EC). The ST then informs the Comms Team that this action is completed.

5. The Comms Team uploads the deliverable on the private space "One Health EJP Consortium Members Group".

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6. All deliverables are **public** and the WP Leader is responsible for uploading them to [Zenodo](#) (Open Access), and to send the [Zenodo](#) link/URL by email to the Comms Team (ohajpcommunications@surrey.ac.uk) who will then accept the [Zenodo](#) entry and put a link on the Deliverables page on the [One Health EJP website](#). The project name should be mentioned in the email sent by the WP Leader to the Comms Team.

Dissemination of Project Deliverables

PMT PROCEDURE

Project Deliverables

Responsibility: Project Leaders (PLs) and Project Collaborators

1. The Project Leader may share the nearly final version by uploading the deliverable to the designated project group on the private space of the [One Health EJP website](#).
2. All deliverables are by default **public**
 - After validation, the Project Leader uploads the deliverable to the Project Group on the [One Health EJP website](#).
 - The Project Leader then uploads the deliverable onto [Zenodo](#).
 - Support for this process can be found in the [Zenodo User Guide](#).
3. Where the deliverable is **confidential** (for instance, in case of a scientific manuscript, be it the manuscript itself or the data supporting it, that cannot be publicised yet), the Project Leader should upload a document that describes the work done (sampling, analysis, more or less the detail of the results, conclusions of the work, etc.). The author of this document chooses the detail, which needs to be sufficiently clear for an external reader to assess the work done.
 - The metadata for the dataset and contact details to the data holder can be found in the project data management plan, which is uploaded on [Zenodo](#) at the end of the project.
4. The Project Leader is requested to justify on the second page of the deliverable why the deliverable is confidential (at this stage).
 - When the status of the document is changed from **confidential** to **public**, the Project Leader follows the previous steps (1, 2).
5. The WP3/WP4 leaders keep track of the project deliverables as a means to monitor the progress of the project.

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PL PROCEDURE

Dissemination of Confidential Project Deliverables PL PROCEDURE

PhD Deliverables

Responsibility: PhD supervisors and PhD students

INTRODUCTION

It is mandatory that all One Health EJP data is published as open research unless the contents of the deliverable need to be temporarily confidential until the PhD project outcomes such as publications are achieved. Once the outcome has been realised, the deliverable contents will become open access. Therefore, any confidentiality is considered temporary, and it is the responsibility of the PhD supervisor to keep the WP6 team informed of any delays to making these deliverables public by emailing WP6.OneHealthEJP@surrey.ac.uk. In exceptional circumstances where confidentiality is required indefinitely, this should be clearly justified.

1. The One Health EJP [PhD Deliverable template](#) must be used for all PhD project deliverables, and can be found under Projects > Templates > Files in the 'PhD projects' group on the members area of the [One Health EJP website](#).

2. The PhD supervisor consults with the PhD team for validation of the deliverable, and in relation to any issues regarding whether the deliverable should be confidential (all deliverables are public by default). This justification should be mentioned in the Document Management section in the deliverable template, and the **Deliverable Confidentiality Statement (Annex 4)**. Also, the author indicates in the Document Management section that the partners that should preferentially be informed about the deliverable (the beneficiaries).

3. **If the deliverable is intended to be temporarily confidential**, a summary of the justification as to why this should be confidential must be provided in the document management table of the deliverable template under 'Dissemination Level'.

4. **In addition, if the deliverable is intended to be temporarily confidential**, the PhD supervisor must also complete the **Deliverable Confidentiality Statement (Annex 4)** which should describe the work that has been done to generate the data or results, and to state that this deliverable is available, but is not open to the public, and the length of embargo.

5. After validation, the PhD supervisor sends the PhD deliverable (and Deliverable Confidentiality Statement if required) by email to the WP6 team - WP6.OneHealthEJP@surrey.ac.uk for effective monitoring of the PhDs.

6. **For both confidential and public deliverables**, the PhD supervisor uploads the finalised deliverable to the **"*PhD project acronym*"** Group on the private space. The PhD deliverables should be uploaded to the Group under "Projects" > **"*PhD acronym* deliverables"** > Files > Upload a File. Please label the file with the deliverable reference. See the website user manual for further instructions on how to upload documents into the "Projects" facility.

7. **For deliverables that are temporarily confidential**, the WP6 Team validate the decision to keep these deliverables confidential, and therefore may discuss with the PhD supervisor and/or PMT on the confidential status of the document if required and should arrive at an agreement in a reasonable period.

8. The WP6 team keeps track of the PhD deliverables to monitor the progress of the project. WP6 sends the document to any beneficiaries as identified.

9. **If the PhD deliverable is a public document**, the PhD supervisor must upload the report to [Zenodo](#) in accordance to instructions in the [Zenodo User Guide](#). On the [Zenodo](#) platform, the PhD supervisor fills in the information and metadata required on the upload form and must include the reference to the One Health EJP grant agreement. *Note: If a publication and/or a data is related to the deliverable, the author must link them in the [Zenodo](#) form. The Comms Team are automatically notified of the upload and will curate and accept the submission.*

10. **If the PhD deliverable is a public document**, the Comms Team will upload the deliverable onto the public project page on the [One Health EJP website](#).

If you have any queries at all regarding this process, please do not hesitate to contact the WP6 Project Manager - p.basu@surrey.ac.uk

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Scientific Publications

1. The lead author of the manuscript (a project collaborator, the PhD student or a PMT member/ collaborator) consults the **One Health EJP Scientific Publication Policy** and carefully follows these instructions.
2. When published, the article is uploaded to [Zenodo](#).
 - When uploading the manuscript to [Zenodo](#), the Project Leader must select the License of the Scientific Journal corresponding with the publication.
 - Support for this process can be found in the **Zenodo User Guide**.
3. If the manuscript is green open access, the manuscript will be made public on [Zenodo](#) after the end of the embargo.
4. If the manuscript is gold open access, the manuscript should be immediately made public on [Zenodo](#) after publication.
5. If a manuscript needs major modifications or is to be submitted to a different journal, the lead author should go through all the steps again (see also the Scientific Publication Policy).
6. The Comms Team puts a link on the [Publications Page](#) on the [One Health EJP website](#).

Dissemination of Project Deliverables

COMMS TEAM PROCEDURES

HOW THE COMMS TEAM WILL DISSEMINATE THE DELIVERABLE

AUDIENCE	INFORMATION	DELIVERABLE CHANNEL	KEY MESSAGES
OHEJP Partners	Public and confidential deliverables	Public deliverable: OHEJP website Zenodo/OpenAire open access repository Article in internal/external newsletters, all or part of a presentation, social media, editorial: author permission sought Confidential deliverable: Closed Project Group on OHEJP website	Transparency of progress Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes Highlight successes Demonstrate use of Grant
OHEJP Stakeholders	Public and confidential deliverables	Public deliverable: OHEJP website Zenodo/OpenAire open access repository Article in internal/external newsletters, all or part of a presentation, social media, editorial: author permission sought	Transparency of progress Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes Highlight successes Demonstrate use of Grant Foster relationships
Policy Makers and International Bodies	Public deliverables	Social media External newsletter OHEJP website Open access repository Editorial PR Networking Personal connections/email	Brand awareness Foster relationships Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes Highlight successes Sustainability of project To affect change
Scientists, Healthcare Professionals - external	Public deliverables	Social media External newsletter OHEJP website Open access repository Email marketing Editorial Conferences and networking	Brand awareness Foster relationships Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes To inform
Students, Early Career Researchers	Public deliverables	Social media External newsletter Open access repository OHEJP website Editorial Conferences and networking	Brand awareness Create the next generation of OHEJP collaborators and One Health scientists To inform and educate
General Public	Public deliverables	Social media PR External newsletter OHEJP website	Image building Brand awareness To inform and educate

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Project Deliverable Templates

Version: 1 / Issue Date: September 2020

Annex 1. Document Management section of the OHEJP deliverables

This is only an extract of the One Health EJP deliverables template which is sent by the Support Team (ohajpcoord@anses.fr, ohajp@sciensano.be) and is also available on [Zenodo](#).

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Title OHEJP Deliverable	
WP and Task	
Leader	
Other Contributors	
Due Month of the Deliverable	
Actual Submission Month	
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: Day-Month-Year
Dissemination Level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

Annex 2. Document Management section of the Project deliverables

This is only an extract of the One Health EJP Project deliverables template which is sent by WP3 (ohjep@sciensano.be) and is also available on [Zenodo](#).

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Project Deliverable	
Project Acronym	
Author	
Other Contributors	
Due Month of the Report	
Actual Submission Month	
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: Day-Month-Year
Dissemination Level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

Annex 3. Document Management section of the PhD deliverables

This is only an extract of the PhD deliverable template which is sent by the WP6 Project Manager (p.basu@surrey.ac.uk) and is also available on the 'PhD Projects' group on the members area of the One Health EJP website.

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Title PhD deliverable	
WP and task	
Leader	
Other Contributors	
Due Month of the Deliverable	
Actual Submission Month	
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: Day-Month-Year
Dissemination Level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU See updated Grant Agreement
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

Annex 4. PhD Deliverable Confidentiality Statement

Please complete the form below, and attach this when submitting any confidential PhD deliverables to the WP6 Team.

It is mandatory that all One Health EJP data is published as open research unless the contents of the deliverable need to be temporarily confidential until the PhD project outcomes such as publications are achieved. Once the outcome has been realised, the deliverable contents will become open access. Therefore, any confidentiality is considered temporary, and it is the responsibility of the PhD supervisor to keep the WP6 team informed of any delays to making these deliverables public by emailing WP6.OneHealthEJP@surrey.ac.uk.

PhD Project Acronym	
Deliverable Number/Ref	
Title of Deliverable	
Submission Month	
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: Day-Month-Year
Dissemination Level <i>CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	CO
Length of Embargo	
End Date of Embargo	If this requires extending, please email WP6.OneHealthEJP@surrey.ac.uk
Overview of Content of Deliverable	Please describe the work that has been done to generate the data or results in as much detail as possible. Please ensure all information provided is suitable for the public.
Confidentiality Statement and Signature	<p>I confirm that that PhD deliverable report has been submitted to the WP6 Team in pdf format and uploaded to the individual PhD project group on the private space of the One Health EJP website as per procedure.</p> <p>Due to the confidentiality of the content, the report will not be available to the public until after the agreed embargo end date.</p> <p>Furthermore, we accept it is our responsibility to inform the WP6 team of any delay to the embargo end date.</p> <p>Date: PhD Supervisor Name: PhD Supervisor Signature: PhD Student Name: PhD Student Signature:</p>

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One Health EJP – The landmark

onehealthjep.eu

About Consortium Projects Training Outcomes ASM

One Health European Joint Programme

A landmark partnership between 37 partners, including acclaimed food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the Med-Vet-Net Association.

LEARN MORE

Website User Manual

MEMBERS AREA USER MANUAL

Version: 1 / Issue Date: September 2020

onehealthjep.eu

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

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This diagram shows a screenshot of the 'One Health European Joint Programme' private group page. The header includes the ne HEALTH EJP logo and the text: 'One Health European Joint Programme'. Below this, it states: 'A landmark partnership between 39 partners, including acclaimed food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the Med-Vet-Net Association.' The page also features a 'Private Group' section with '3 days ago' and 'GROUP ADMINS' with profile pictures. A search bar contains the text 'Find all key project documents and...' and a 'LEAVE GROUP' button. At the bottom, there is a navigation menu with icons for: HOME, FORUM, DOCUMENTS, MEMBERS, SEND INVITES, PROJECTS, MEDIA, and MANAGE. A 'SHOW: -EVERYTHING-' dropdown menu is visible at the bottom right.

ABOUT

The One Health EJP website (www.onehealthjep.eu) has a public interface but also boasts a private space. **Only members of the OHEJP consortium can register to use the private space of the website to create their own account using their institute email address.**

This document is intended to help members to navigate and use the private space features, and to facilitate communication and collaboration across the website.

Contact Us

If you require assistance with any aspect of the website, or would like to provide some feedback, please contact the Communications Team.

Communications Team		
Piyali Basu	WP6 Communications (UoS)	p.basu@surrey.ac.uk
Jade Passey (main website contact)	Digital Communications (UoS)	jade.passey@surrey.ac.uk
Elaine Campling	Creative Communications (UoS)	e.campling@surrey.ac.uk

Browser

We recommend using **Google Chrome** or **Mozilla Firefox** browsers. If you use Internet Explorer, please be aware not all features (including the download facility) are supported by this browser.

Website Registration

Only members of the OHEJP consortium can register to use the private space of the website to create their own account using their institute email address.

Once you have registered for the OHEJP website, your request needs to be validated by the Communications Officer. This process can take up to 3 working days.

Follow the following steps to register on the website:

Step 1: Visit <https://onehealthjep.eu/> and click on "Register".

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Step 2: Fill in the registration details.

Please ensure that you use your institute email address and fill out **all** of the boxes, including the **please specify** boxes.

Your Profile

You can view and edit your profile once you have created an account. We recommend that each member uploads a picture of themselves to make themselves easily identifiable to other members. Furthermore, it is your responsibility to make sure that your profile is up to date, for example, if your role changes, please update your profile.

To view your profile, please follow the following steps:

Step 1: From the homepage, click on "Members" in the top right-hand corner.

Step 2: In the search bar, search for your profile and click on to it.

Step 3: Click on "Profile".

Step 4: Your profile can be edited from here, including adding a photo. Once your profile has been edited, be sure to click "Save". From here, other features can be explored, such as your notifications, messages and groups etc.

Groups

Understanding the Groups

INTRODUCTION

Once you have joined the website, you can join any relevant groups for example, project groups.

The groups on the private space of the website are a facility to allow members to collaborate, create discussion forums, upload files, add and track deliverables and milestones. Each OHEJP Work Package and Joint Research and Joint Integrative Project has its own group. These groups are managed by the group administrator and managed as determined by the administrator.

Existing Groups

To explore the existing groups, follow the following steps.

Step 1: From the homepage, click on "Groups" in the top right-hand corner.

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Step 2: View all of the groups on the private space. These groups can be searched in the "Search Groups" bar, or you can scroll through the list of current groups.

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One Health EJP Consortium Members Group

All One Health EJP Consortium Members are asked to join the “[OHEJP Consortium Members](#)” Group. This group contains all of OHEJP templates, procedures and key information that consortium members may need.

Step 1: To find this group, search “OHEJP Consortium Members” in the search bar and click on the group.

Step 2: To request to join the group, click “Request Membership”. Membership requests will be approved within 1 working day.

Step 3: Once you have access to the group, you can access all of documents and updates.

SHOW: — EVERYTHING —

What's new in OHEJP Consortium Members, University?

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Project Groups

To join the project groups, the process is the same. Search for the desired project in the search bar and follow the steps detailed above.

Group Roles and Responsibilities

There are different levels of responsibility in the groups, these include **administrators, moderators and members**. The different levels are managed by the group administrator.

Group administrators

Highest level of authority.

- Send invites
- Can promote or demote the status of members according to access requirements
- Can edit or delete the group itself
- Accept or reject membership request
- Create discussion forum
- Upload and share documents.

Group moderators

One level down from administrators.

- Can perform the same actions as group admins can, but they cannot edit or delete the group
- Able to upload and share documents.

Group members

Group member.

- Can only view and download documents
- Able to upload and share documents
- Create discussion forum.

Creating a New Group

New groups can be created within the private space to facilitate information sharing and collaboration.

Step 1: Click on “Groups” in the top right-hand corner of the screen.

Step 2: Click on “Create a Group”.

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Step 3: Fill out all of the details of your group and click “Create Group and Continue”.

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Step 4: If you would like a forum within your group, tick “Yes. I want this group to have a forum”. Then click “Next Step”.

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Step 5: A photo can be added to the group to make it more distinguishable.

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Step 6: A cover photo can also be added to the group.

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Step 7: Invite member to the group by ticking the box next to their name.

Functionalities within the groups

Inviting other users to the group (administrators and moderators)

As the administrator or moderator of a group, you may want to invite other members to join the group. Most of the groups on the One Health EJP website are private and require either an invite to a request for membership.

As an administrator or moderator, follow the following steps to invite an existing website user to your group:

Step 1: Enter your group (the WORLDCOM group is used as an example here, but this applies to all groups). Click on "Send Invites".

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Step 2: Scroll through the list of website members and tick the boxes of the members you wish to invite to your group. Once you have selected all of the members, click “Send Invites”.

You can also send invitations by email to those that are not already members on the website.

Accepting users into the group (administrators)

As the group administrator, you are responsible for managing the access to your group. Each time a member requests to join your group you will receive an email. If you click on the link it will directly take you to a screen where you can accept or reject that request.

If you would like to view the number requests in your group, follow the following steps:

Step 1: Enter your group and click on “Manage”.

Step 2: Click on “Requests” and then there will be a list of members who have requested access. Click “Accept” or “Reject” as appropriate.

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Defining the roles of users in the group (administrators)

Once members have been accepted into the group, their role can be edited to give them more responsibilities within the group. Follow the following steps to learn how to promote (and demote) group members.

Step 1: Once you are in the group, click "Manage".

Step 2: Click on "Members".

Step 3: In the "Members" list, all members and their roles will be displayed.

As a group administrator there are several options:

- Promote to admin
- Promote to mod
- Remove from the group
- Kick & Ban.

Click on these buttons to take the appropriate action.

Uploading documents into the group

There are two ways in which to store documents in the groups, using the “Documents” option or the “Projects” options.

The “Documents” option uploads documents into a list, the document can only be organised using tags. **This option is most suitable where only a small number of documents will be uploaded to the group.**

The “Projects” option allows documents to be uploaded into folders and sub folders. **This option is the best option if lots of documents are going to be uploaded into the group.**

Using the “Documents” option while in the group:

Step 1: Click on “Documents” (as above).

Step 2: Click on “Add New”.

Step 3: Fill in the form and upload the file.

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Step 4: The files can be categorised by using an existing category (as with the example below), if categories haven't been previously used, a new category can be created using the "New Category" field.

Step 5: Click "Save" at the bottom of the page.

Category:

- 191113 KOM 2nd call projects Berlin
- Communication Procedures
- Contractual Documents
- Deliverables
- Deliverables WP2
- Deliverables WP3

New Category...!

Save

Using the "Projects" option to create document folders in the group:

Step 1: Click on "Projects" (as above).

Step 2: Click on "New Project".

HOME FORUM DOCUMENTS MEMBERS SEND INVITES **PROJECTS** MANAGE

Project Manager **New Project** Search ...

Active Completed Favourite All

Stakeholder Activity Documents: Each month, Work Package 5 create a document that lists...

OHEJP Annual Scientific Meetings: All of the documents from the OHEJP ASMs, including abstract...

Scientific Project Selection: Details of the scientific projects funded by the OHEJP.

Communication Tools: Contains all OHEJP templates (meeting minutes, attendance...

Step 3: Fill in the "Start a new project" box with the details of the folder you wish to create. Followed by clicking on the "Add New Project" button.

Start a new project

Deliverables and Milestones

- Project Category -

Some details about the project (optional)

Notify Co-Workers

Add New Project Cancel

Step 4: Once the “Project” has been created click on “Files” (other options on this top menu bar can also be explored if you wish to add milestones with deadlines etc).

Step 5: Click on “Create a folder”.

Step 6: Add the details in the “Create a folder” box, then click “Create a folder”.

Step 7: Now that the folder has been created, double click on it (please note that you must double click on the folder to open it, a single click will not work).

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Step 8: Upload files into this folder using the “Upload a file” button.

Key points:

- Documents up to 1GB can be uploaded
- Allowed file formats - odt, ods, rtf, txt, doc, docx, xls, xlsx, ppt, pps, pptx, ppsx, pdf, jpg, jpeg, gif, png, zip, tar, gz
- Only group members can access these documents
- **Important reminder: The sensitivity and confidentiality of documents should be considered when uploading documents into the group. Please seek to gain permission from the relevant lead person if necessary.**

To accept/reject an invite to a group

If you have been invited to a group, this invite will be sent to you via email, but can also be viewed in your notifications (see [Your Profile](#) section above).

Once you can see the notification under the [Your Profile](#) section, follow the following steps to accept your request.

Step 1: Find the notification and click on it.

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Step 2: Click "Accept" or "Reject" in the bottom right hand corner.

Looking for how to request membership to a group? This can be found under **Groups** in this manual.

Creating discussion forms

Creating discussion forums can be a useful tool to collaborate across the project consortium. All group members can create forums.

Step 1: In your chosen group, click on "Forum".

Step 2: Scroll down to "Create New Topic" and fill out the necessary details and then click "Submit" in the bottom right hand corner. The forum topics will then appear in a list under the "Forum" tab.

Create New Topic in "Private: University of Surrey Communications"

Your account has the ability to post unrestricted HTML content.

Topic Title (Maximum Length: 80):

Topic Tags:

Topic Type:

Normal

Topic Status:

Step 3: Once forums have been created, they can be subscribed to by clicking the “Subscribe” button.

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Project Management on the One Health EJP website

The One Health EJP website has a project management facility on the private space that is incorporated into all of the groups. This tool could be useful for managing task and creating different projects and milestones within each group.

Creating tasks

The creation of projects is described on page 16. Within these projects, tasks can be created. To create a task:

Step 1: Click on the project that you wish to create tasks for and click on “Task Lists”.

Step 2: Click on “+ Add Task List”.

Step 3: When the task has been set up, subtasks can be defined within that task. Click on the task created in the task list. Then use the “+ Add new task” button to create subtasks.

Step 4: During the creation of tasks, you can do several tasks:

- (i) To make a task private, click on the icon.
- (ii) To give additional details of the task, click on the icon.
- (iii) To assign a task to a group member, click on the icon.
- (iv) To assign a date to the group, click on the icon.

Please note: After specifying your start date and end date, **you must click out of the calendar and then PRESS REFRESH in order to update the deadline correctly.** If you do not press refresh, the deadline will not be updated.

- (v) To confirm the task, click on the icon.

Creating Milestones

Project milestones can be created to track the progress of different aspects of the project.

These can be set up as follows:

Step 1: Within the group “Projects” tab, click on “Milestones”.

Step 2: Click on “Add Milestone”.

Step 3: Complete the details of the milestone and then click.

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Step 4: The milestones can then be viewed in a list under “Upcoming Milestones”.

Your Dashboard

All of your profile specific projects and tasks assigned to you can be viewed in the Dashboard. The Dashboard can be entered from the homepage of the website.

Step 1: From the top menu bar, projects and tasks assigned to your account can be viewed. Everything can be monitored from here, additionally this can be viewed as a calendar which presents deadlines of tasks in a more user-friendly way.

My Events

We encourage all OHEJP events to be added to the website. Support and advice from the Communications Team is also available. If the event is free, the ticketing system can be used to collect registration information from attendees, please contact the Communications Team regarding this.

If you are organising an OHEJP event, please inform the Communications Team using the Communications Mailbox: OHEJPCommunications@surrey.ac.uk. Also, following your event, please do not forget to complete the [OHEJP Internal Events Survey](#).

Step 1: "My Events" can be entered from the homepage of the website.

Step 2: Click on “Add New” to add a new event. Your current events will be listed below.

Step 3: Complete all of the details in the form below and click “Submit Event”.

Step 4: Your submitted events can be found under the “News” tab on the front end of the website, then under “Events and Announcements”.

Current Events

Show only the first upcoming instance of recurring events

DATE	SEARCH	NEAR	FIND EVENTS	VIEW AS
Date	Keyword	Location	FIND EVENTS	Photo

Previous Events

First One Health EJP CPD Module March 12 - March 13 OHEJP Consortium Events	One Health EJP Scientific Steering Board (SSB) Meeting March 19 OHEJP Consortium Events	Antimicrobial Resistance Summit 2020 March 19 OHEJP Topic-related Events
Symposium: Filling the knowledge gaps in animal disease control April 29 OHEJP Topic-related Events	4th International Conference on Animal Health Surveillance - Bridging Science and Policy May 12 - May 14 OHEJP Topic-related Events	Practical use of NGS data webinar April 29 @ 9:00 am - 12:00 pm OHEJP Consortium Events
One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting		One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting

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Zenodo User Guide

UPLOADING PUBLICATIONS AND DELIVERABLES TO ZENODO

Zenodo is an open access repository developed by the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit datasets, research software, reports, deliverables and publications, which in turn facilitates the ease of access of this information to the wider scientific community. Open access data systems must ensure that data follow the **FAIR** principles, thus data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable which promotes the maximum use of research data. When data are open access it promotes collaborations and reduces duplication of work, which are also important aims in the One Health EJP.

The One Health EJP requires its scientific outcomes to be publicly available where possible, and as soon as possible.

Please carefully read the metadata requirements when uploading public deliverables and publications.

For any technical support, please contact ohjep@sciensano.be

Here is a step by step guide to uploading a document to Zenodo.

1. Log in to Zenodo

Step 1: Visit <https://zenodo.org>

Step 2: Create an account (by clicking on **Sign up**) or log in to your existing account (by clicking on **Log in**).

Recent uploads

June 8, 2020 (v1.3) Report Open Access View
The Pan-SL-CoV/GD sequences may be from contamination.
 Daoyu Zhang
 ABSTRACT Recently, There were much hype about an alleged SARS-like coronavirus being found in samples of Malayan

Need help?
 Contact us
 Zenodo prioritizes all requested related to the COVID-19 outbreak.
 We can help with:

2. "Upload" sections

Step 1: Click "Upload".

Recent uploads

June 8, 2020 (v1.3) Report Open Access View
The Pan-SL-CoV/GD sequences may be from contamination.
 Daoyu Zhang
 ABSTRACT Recently, There were much hype about an alleged SARS-like coronavirus being found in samples of Malayan pangolins (Manis javanica) possessing nearly identical RBD to the SARS CoV 2 coronavirus. Prominent journals cite the alleged discovery to claim that pangolins may be one of a...
Uploaded on May 19, 2021
 12 more version(s) exist for this record

Need help?
 Contact us
 Zenodo prioritizes all requested related to the COVID-19 outbreak.
 We can help with:

- Uploading your research data, software, preprints, etc.
- One-on-one with Zenodo supporters.
- Quota increases beyond our default policy.

Step 2: Click “New Upload”. The upload page appears.

On the upload page, the following sections appear:

- Files
- Communities
- Upload type
- Basic information
- License
- Funding

You should fill them as indicated below.

3. Upload a document to Zenodo

3.1. “Files” section

This section serves to upload the document to the system.

Step 1: Upload your file by clicking on “Choose files” then selecting on your computer the file to be uploaded.

Step 2: Once your file appears under “Filename”, click “Start upload”. (Please note that it is impossible to publish the document if you have not clicked on “Start upload” before.)

3.2. “Communities” section

This section serves to select the community under which you intend to upload the document (in this case it is One Health EJP).

Step 1: Scroll down to “Communities” and type “OHEJP” and click on “One Health EJP”. Your upload will be added to the One Health EJP Community.

3.3. “Upload type” section

This section serves to describe the type of upload: journal article, project deliverable, etc.

Step 1: If the document to upload is a Journal article or a project deliverable, select “Publication”.

Step 2: A list appears under publication type (“Journal article” or “Project deliverable”).

NB: in step 1 and step 2 we have presented the main OHEJP documents types (“Journal article” and “Project deliverable”). Other options may be chosen if needed (“Poster”, “Presentation”, “Other”, etc.).

3.4. “Basic information” section

In this section identification, titles and keywords are required.

Step 1: If the document already has a DOI, please copy it and paste it in the “Digital Object Identifier” section. Otherwise, leave empty.

Basic information required ▾

Digital Object Identifier

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Step 2: Fill in the publication date.

Publication date *

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Step 3: If the document to upload is a publication, provide the official title. If the document to upload is a deliverable, enter the deliverable number and the full title (e.g. “Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 SOP on detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce matrix” or “D-JRP8-4.2 Overview of Metastava output”).

Title *

Required.

Step 4: Enter the Author(s) name(s).

Authors *

Optional.

Step 5: Under “Description” enter the name of the project that the publication relates to, for example: “JRP-TOXOSOURCES” or “OHEJP Project: COHESIVE”. This can be followed by a brief description of the document.

Description *

Step 6: Under “Keywords” enter the One Health EJP project name (ex: Listadapt, MedVetKlebs...) and any other main keywords relevant for the document. The keywords are important metadata that help to make the document findable (the first point of FAIR-principle).

Keywords

Enter the first keyword in the empty field.

Keywords

If you need to add a new keyword: click on “+Add another keyword”. A new empty field appears, in which you can type the second keyword. (Repeat as many times as needed.)

Keywords

[+Add another keyword](#)

3.5. "License" section

In this section, information about the access rights and the License type are required.

Step 1: Select the Access right

- "Open Access": by default (Gold open access, or Green open access after the end of the embargo)
- "Embargoed Access": Green open access during the max. 6 month embargo period (if you choose this access type, you need to change it to "Open Access" at the end of the embargo period)
- "Restricted Access": discouraged
- "Closed Access": discouraged.

The screenshot shows the 'License' section of the Zenodo interface. The 'Access right' dropdown menu is open, showing four options: 'Open Access' (selected), 'Embargoed Access', 'Restricted Access', and 'Closed Access'. A red box highlights the 'Open Access' option. Below the menu, a note states: 'required: Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.'

Step 2: Select the correct "License".

For publications, make sure to select the License of the Scientific Journal corresponding with the publication).

The default License that Zenodo suggests is the "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International" (CC-BY-4.0), other options appear as drop down menu when you start writing the name of the license.

The screenshot shows the 'License' section of the Zenodo interface. The 'License' dropdown menu is open, showing 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International' selected. A red box highlights the selected license. Below the menu, a note states: 'Required: Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the Other licenses available (Other (Open), Other (Attribution), etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and sdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please contact us.'

Zenodo has hundreds of license options in the database, and there is also option 'Other'. <https://blog.zenodo.org/2018/11/22/2018-11-22-new-licenses/>

3.6. "Funding" section

In this section the grant number is requested (for OHEJP: 773830).

Step 1: in the empty field, type "773830".

The screenshot shows the 'Funding' section of the Zenodo interface. The 'Grants' dropdown menu is open, showing 'European Commission (EU)' selected. The grant number '773830' is entered in the adjacent text field. A red box highlights the grant number. Below the menu, a note states: 'Optional: OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding agencies, a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your uploads.' A blue box highlights the grant details: 'One Health EJP 773830 Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.'

Step 2: click on "One Health EJP 773830".

The screenshot shows the 'Funding' section of the Zenodo interface. The 'Grants' dropdown menu is open, showing 'European Commission (EU)' selected. The grant number '773830' is entered in the adjacent text field. A red box highlights the grant number. Below the menu, a note states: 'Optional: OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding agencies, a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your uploads.' A blue box highlights the grant details: 'One Health EJP 773830 Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.'

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3.7. Other sections

Complete any other relevant information if you wish.

Related/alternate identifiers	recommended >
Contributors	optional >
References	optional >
Journal	optional >
Conference	optional >
Book/Report/Chapter	optional >
Thesis	optional >
Subjects	optional >

4. Save and publish the document

Step 1: Finalise the upload by clicking “Save”.

References	optional >
Journal	optional >
Conference	optional >
Book/Report/Chapter	optional >
Thesis	optional >
Subjects	optional >

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[OAI-PMH](#)
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[Infrastructure](#)
[What's New](#)

[Principles](#)

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Funded by

Step 2: Click on “Publish”.

References	optional >
Journal	optional >
Conference	optional >
Book/Report/Chapter	optional >
Thesis	optional >
Subjects	optional >

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[Features](#)
[OAI-PMH](#)
[Donate](#)

[Infrastructure](#)
[What's New](#)

[Principles](#)

[Contact](#)

Funded by

Step 3: The following message appears. Click on “I understand”.

Saved successfully.

Warning

Once the record is published you will no longer be able to change the files in this upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be registered immediately after publishing. You will still be able to update the record's metadata later.

If you only want to create a test upload, please do so on Zenodo Sandbox.

New upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in metadata.

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Test.docx	13 kB	✓	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>

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@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

5. Editing the document

The author of the document is the only person able to edit the document after it has been published.

Step 1: Click on your document.

zenodo.org/record/4244116#.YKdp2qgzZM0

November 4, 2020

Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via multicopy plasmid encapsidation mediated by temperate phages

I. Irena Rodríguez-Rubín, Carlos Serna, Manuel Ares-Arroyo, Rosco R. Maramoros, José F. Delgado-Blas, Natalia Montero, Cristina Bernabe Balas, Emilia F. Wedel, Irene S. Mendez, Maite Muniaca, Bruno González-Zorn

Objectives: To investigate the relevance of multicopy plasmids in antimicrobial resistance and assess their mobilization mediated by phage particles

Methods: Several databases with complete sequences of plasmids and annotated genes were analysed. The 16S methyltransferase gene armA conferring high level aminoglycoside resistance was used as a marker in eight different plasmids, from different incompatibility groups, and with differing sizes and plasmid copy numbers. All plasmids were transformed into Escherichia coli bearing one of four different lysogenic phages. Upon induction, encapsidation of armA in phage particles was evaluated using qRT-PCR and Southern blotting.

Results: Multicopy plasmids carry a vast set of emerging clinically important antimicrobial resistance genes. However, 60% of these plasmids do not bear mobility (MOB) genes. When carried on these multicopy plasmids, mobilization of a marker gene armA into phage capsids was up to 10000 times more frequent than when it was

38 views, 26 downloads

Communities: One Health EJP

OpenAIRE

Step 2: Click on "Edit".

zenodo.org/record/4244116#.YKdp2qgzZM0

November 4, 2020

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38 views, 26 downloads

Communities: One Health EJP

OpenAIRE

Step 3: You can now make updates and then click on "Save".

zenodo.org

Upload Communities

Discard changes Save Publish

Edit upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press "Save" to save your upload for editing later. (iii) When ready, press "Publish" to finalize and make your upload public.

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization vi... md5:59c89dae5a33191f3e5a7a9a166cd171	580 kB	✓	🗑️

Note: File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is registered with DataCite for each upload. (minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)

If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ section on file upload issues.

Communities recommended

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Step 4: Click on "Publish".

6. Accepting the document in the OHEJP community

Please inform the Communications Team at OHEJPCommunications@surrey.ac.uk and send them the Zenodo URL of the upload. They will accept the submission in the OHEJP Community.

Once you have published the submission you will be able to view the upload. The URL can be found here:

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Scientific Publication Policy

WP3 JOINT RESEARCH PROJECTS
WP4 JOINT INTEGRATIVE PROJECTS

Responsible Partner: INSA
Contributing partners: SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 773830
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement No. 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	Scientific Publication Policy version 3
WP and task	WP4
Author	INSA
Other contributors	SVA
Due month of the report	-
Actual submission month	M43
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 6-Jul-21
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s): JRP/JIP project leaders, PhD students and their supervisors</p>

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION POLICY

1. Introduction

INTRODUCTION

This One Health EJP (OHEJP) Scientific Publication Policy sets out guidelines for written scientific outputs submitted via a peer-reviewed process under the OHEJP.

COMMS STRATEGY

The main purpose of this policy is to guarantee that the OHEJP scientific outputs are published to the maximum possible scientific standard, using a coordinated and appropriate approach. This is important in order to standardize messages from the consortium, to ensure speedy publication of scientific results, to avoid conflicts of authorship, to be transparent about any conflicts of interest, and to take into account the legitimate interests of all parties and owners of scientific results. This approach will guarantee that all researchers benefit from their involvement to the OHEJP consortium.

DISSEMINATION

The Scientific Publication Policy describes the flow of scientific publications, from their drafting to finalisation. The policy is based on the commitments made by parties in the H2020 Grant Agreement and the OHEJP Consortium Agreement provisions and the Uniform Requirements for Authorship listed above, as well as to procedures laid down in the OHEJP Data Management Plan.

PROJECT DELIVERABLE TEMPLATES

In case of disputes related to this publication policy, the specific JRP/JIP Project Leader (PL) will be contacted to arrive at an agreement. If required, OHEJP WP3/WP4 Leaders and the OHEJP Coordination Team (CT) may also be informed; their assessment will be based on OHEJP consortium interests.

It is extra important to remember

- to publish gold or green open access; and
- to follow the project procedure to anchor the decision to publish results; and
- to acknowledge the OHEJP.

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2. Definitions

According to the HORIZON 2020 online manual.

Green open access (self-archiving): the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed. Open access to the publication must be ensured within at most 6 months.

Gold open access (open-access publishing): an article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers.

ZENODO USER MANUAL

3. Scope of the OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy

This policy covers **all types of scientific material published in a peer-reviewed process** such as research publications in scientific journals and other scientific materials e.g., conference abstracts. **However, papers uploaded in bioRxiv/medRxiv/other similar should also follow this policy.** National publications should build on already published international results.

Press releases, leaflets, brochures, reports, and other public communications are not in the scope of the Scientific Publication Policy. In this case, the authors should read the Dissemination procedure as well as the Communication Strategy document to find out how to proceed.

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4. Producing scientific publications

The OHEJP Project Management Team (PMT) encourages researchers to stimulate the publication of scientific articles and other outputs in order to widely (qualitatively and quantitatively) disseminate the findings of each JRP, JIP and PhD project, during the project. The aim is that within 12 months after the end of the project all outputs should be published.

INTRODUCTION

It is mandatory that all partners publish OHEJP research as open access publications (gold or green), using scientific leading international peer-reviewed journals in the respective field of research. The gold open access is preferred to the green open access, since it allows immediate dissemination without an embargo period. Independently of chosen strategy, the article must be made publicly available at the latest 6 months after publication according to HORIZON 2020 rules. Some journals have a longer embargo period than 6 months, these journals should not be chosen for publication of OHEJP research work.

COMMS STRATEGY

OHEJP partners must make every effort to disseminate results rapidly (as soon as they are publishable), in order to feed evidence into the tight timeframes under an evolving policy agenda.

The lead author of an OHEJP scientific publication should inform the specific JRP/JIP PL and all the remaining project participants well in advance of submission. No paper or abstract must be submitted nor published before all co-authors have reviewed the publication and given their formal written approval (using any media). Similarly, the PhD student must inform the supervisor and co-authors of the intention to prepare a scientific publication.

DISSEMINATION

During the peer-review process and prior to submission of the final draft, all authors must be consulted on any changes to the publication through the lead author.

The same workflow should be followed by any non-project member of the OHEJP aiming to submit an OHEJP scientific publication. In this case the submission should be approved by the PMT.

N.B. Inform the JRP/JIP project leader about the date for when the embargo period ends and the publication fee. This information will be included in project reports.

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5. Overview of other principles for publishing

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** sets out the requirements for ensuring data confidentiality and integrity when handling data. The lead author is responsible for the individuals handling data in the production of a publication to ensure that these requirements are respected.

Thus, where the publication uses OHEJP data, as OHEJP consortium partners will have direct access to a list of studies and relevant metadata generated via OHEJP JRP, JIPs or PhD project data, the lead author must respect the procedures set out in the project specific DMP and the OHEJP overarching DMP in order to access the data (both documents can be found on the private space on the website). The lead author is responsible for ensuring that these procedures are correctly followed when using OHEJP data accessed via the OHEJP repository to support a publication or any conference abstract — contacting the data owner and/or data provider at least 30 days prior to submission of any articles for publication, providing the title, abstract and author list — and must then invite the data owners to be co-authors of the publication (the data owner and/or data provider may propose a maximum of two co-authors).

Any project participant may object to a publication for patent reasons or to request deletion of a participant's Confidential Information. Such objection must be submitted in writing to the specific JRP/JIP PL within 15 days of notification. If this objection is approved by the PL, the publishing participant will modify the publication as requested for patent reasons and/or delete such other participant's confidential information from the intended publication.

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6. Authorship

Following the Uniform Requirements for Authorship and Contributorship from the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (www.icmje.org), authorship credit is based on:

1. substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data; and
2. drafting the article or revising it critically for important intellectual content; and
3. final approval of the version to be published.

For particular publications, consortium authorship can be used. The lead author can then add “*on behalf of One Health EJP/JRP/JIP/PhD project [acronym]*” at the end of the list of authors. This request may be made by the PL when providing feedback on the publication proposal. If the journal specifically refuses this mention in the authorship, it should be added in acknowledgments, and the web address for the OHEJP website should be cited.

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7. Ethics

The authors must include text to confirm that all animal or human research has been conducted according to ethical legislations, even if this information is not explicitly requested by the journal. In addition, it should be stated that the OHEJP also has put in place a strict monitoring of the ethical issues and is bound to it through a precise check by external ethical advisors. The manuscript must follow the journal's requirements (e.g., ethical approval authorities and numbers).

8. Publication and Intellectual Property

All OHEJP participants are encouraged to publish results in a timely fashion (as soon as results are publishable). It is acceptable to delay publication to allow partners to achieve suitable Intellectual Property protection (see Section 5.5.6.2. of DMP from OHEJP). However, this delay is not allowed to be longer than the specified embargo period associated with the data being submitted, which might be from 6 to 12 months from the completion of the data analysis (see article 29.2 of Grant Agreement).

Note which "License" for publications is applicable for the chosen journal, since all publications according to the [Dissemination Procedure](#) should be uploaded in Zenodo and the default License that Zenodo suggests is the "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International" (CC-BY-4.0), even if other options are available.

9. Disclosure information

If applicable, a statement about author's disclosure should be included in manuscripts, according to the guidelines of the journal.

10. Acknowledgements of EU funding and the One Health EJP

All scientific publications that include or build on OHEJP results, data or materials must specify that the project has received EU research support and funding. Acknowledgement must be performed with the following text:

"This work was supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme."

Note that:

- Where possible in publication types, the European Union flag should be included, and when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
- Abstracts or papers partially including OHEJP data should mention it appropriately.
- In cases where OHEJP partners produce a publication that refers to OHEJP, but does not actually draw on results produced under the initiative, partners are asked to acknowledge OHEJP.
- Publications that are not the result of research carried out under the OHEJP project should not be acknowledged to OHEJP.
- The inclusion of OHEJP subjects in another study (abstract or manuscript) without sharing of data from OHEJP does not need any form of mention.

These instructions are independent of those of other financing organisations that may have provided funds for the research.

11. Archive and access to publications

The Scientific Publication Policy should be read in conjunction with the [Dissemination Procedure](#) and [Communication Strategy documents](#), e.g., in order to inform all OHEJP consortium partners about an accepted peer-reviewed publication in a scientific journal and to make it available on the OHEJP website.

12. Consequences of non-compliance

For non-compliance, see article 29.6 and 43 of Grant Agreement, resulting of possible rejection of declared costs in relation with the publication and a reduction of the total EU Grant.

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Primary Colors

Burnt Orange
#F47931
RGB 244 121 49
CMYK 0 0.50 0.80 0.04

Cerulean
#00679C
RGB 0 103 156
CMYK 1 0.34 0 0.39

Very Light Grey
#CECECE
RGB 206 206 206
CMYK 0 0 0 0.19

Color Palette

#414042
RGB 65 64 66
CMYK 0.02 0.03 0 0.74

#719A9E
RGB 113 154 158
CMYK 59 28 35 11

#63913E
RGB 99 145 62
CMYK 0.32 0 0.57 0.43

#41B7E1
RGB 65 183 225
CMYK 0.71 0.19 0 0.12

#82A765
RGB 130 167 101
CMYK 0.22 0 0.40 0.35

#67C5E7
RGB 103 197 231
CMYK 0.15 0 0.09

#9BB984
RGB 155 183 133
CMYK 0.21 0.15 0.40 0.21

Brand Communications

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onehealthjrp.eu

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

BRAND COMMUNICATIONS

Effective communications can contribute to the objectives of the consortium by:

- building common understanding of audiences and priorities
- helping to explain policy and delivery
- create continuity in communications activity
- articulate objectives and measures of success
- facilitating collaborations between the institutes
- deliver appropriate social and economic impact based on the results
- results from the project are communicated to target audiences.

FLOW OF INFORMATION

Relevant information in a timely flow through the established procedure is paramount to achieving our objectives.

The infographic outlines the correct procedure for an effective and efficient flow of information.

Communications Team Support Services	
Piyali Basu p.basu@surrey.ac.uk	OHEJP Communications Strategy and Planning WP6 Education and Training activities Project Manager <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communications, Strategy, Planning and Reporting of WP6 Education and Training activities • Doctoral Programme • Short Term Missions • Summer Schools • Continuing Professional Development modules • Communication and Media workshop • ASM Satellite Workshops • Point of Contact: Support for applications to organise WP6 training events, or participate in the WP6 Education activities
Jade Passey jade.passey@surrey.ac.uk	OHEJP Digital Communications Strategy and Planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Contact Persons point of contact • Scientific copywriting • Website content creation and management • Social media accounts content creation and management • Digital internal and external newsletters creation and management
Elaine Campling e.campling@surrey.ac.uk	OHEJP Creative Communications Strategy and Planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand positioning • Internal events communications content creation and management • External event communications content creation and management • Graphic communications - infographics, logo creation, icons, image sourcing • Merchandise

OHEJP BRANDING

The OHEJP branding is fundamental for several key reasons:

1. It improves the visibility of the OHEJP
2. It helps to establish the OHEJP as a reputable brand in both the scientific community, stakeholders, policy makers and the general public
3. It aids with the sustainability of the OHEJP after the lifetime of the project.

The Communication Team at Surrey has developed a [branding guide](#) for the OHEJP which includes the following:

1. The OHEJP logo
 1. In several formats including the master logo and the logo for a dark background
 2. A colour palate
 3. A primary and secondary typeface
 4. A QR code
 5. Validated One Health Venn diagrams.

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This branding guide should be used when creating any OHEJP documentation, graphics and promotional material.

MASTER LOGO

[Joint Research and Joint Integrative Project Logos](#)

[PhD Project Logos](#)

All logos have been sent to the PhD supervisors of these respective projects.

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@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

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Burnt Orange
#F47931
RGB 244 121 49
CMYK 0 0.50 0.80 0.044

Cerulean
#00679C
RGB 0 103 156
CMYK 1 0.34 0 0.39

Very Light Grey
#CECECE
RGB 206 206 206
CMYK 0 0 0 0.19

SECONDARY COLOURS

#414042
RGB 65 64 66
CMYK 0.02 0.03 0 0.74

#719A9E
R113 G154 B158
C59 M28 Y35 K1

#63913E
RGB 99 145 62
CMYK 0.32 0 0.57 0.43

#606060
RGB 96 96 96
CMYK 0 0 0 0.62

#41B7E1
RGB 65 183 225
CMYK 0.71 0.19 0 0.12

#82A765
RGB 130 167 101
CMYK 0.22 0 0.40 0.35

#7A7A7A
RGB 122 122 122
CMYK 0 0 0 0.52

#67C5E7
RGB 103 197 231
CMYK 0.55 0.15 0 0.09

#9BB984
RGB 155 185 132
CMYK 0.16 0 0.29 0.27

#A3A3A3
RGB 163 163 163
CMYK 0 0 0 0.36

#85D1EC
RGB 133 209 236
CMYK 0.44 0.11 0 0.07

#AFC79D
RGB 175 199 157
CMYK 0.12 0 0.21 0.22

#D6D6D6
RGB 214 214 214
CMYK 0 0 0 0.16

#9DDAF0
RGB 157 218 240
CMYK 0.35 0.09 0 0.06

#BFD2B1
RGB 191 210 177
CMYK 0.09 0 0.16 0.18

PRIMARY TYPEFACE

Open Sans

The Open Sans font can be downloaded: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Open+Sans>

“The One Health European Joint Project is a landmark partnership consisting of 44 partners”
Open Sans (Google Font)

“The One Health European Joint Project is a landmark partnership consisting of 44 partners”
Open Sans Italic (Google Font)

“The One Health European Joint Project is a landmark partnership consisting of 44 partners”
Open Sans Semibold (Google Font)

Arial can be used as a substitute where necessary.

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VISION

We recognise that human health is tightly connected to the health of animals and the environment.

One Health EJP (OHEJP) will reinforce collaborations and integrate public health, animal health and food safety in order to improve research on the prevention and control of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

AIMS

Through collaboration between our food, veterinary and medical partners, the OHEJP aims to harmonise approaches for the assessment and management of foodborne zoonotic infections, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across Europe.

Using an interdisciplinary and integrative approach to One Health challenges we aim to improve the quality and compatibility of information. This will assist in decision making to equip risk managers and policy makers with the best tools for intervention measures at the policy level.

TARGET AUDIENCES

- Policy makers and stakeholders
- OHEJP governance bodies
- OHEJP partner institutes
 - Scientists
 - Students and early career researchers
- Potential influencers and new members
- General public.

COMMS CHANNELS

Ensure appropriate distribution of key communications while recognising and preventing communication overload: website, internal and external newsletters, reports, editorial, conferences, networking, workshops, social media, email marketing.

TIMELINE AND MILESTONES

In line with the Grant Agreement: 60 months commencing 1 January 2018. List of deliverables milestones as set out in the Grant Agreement.

VISION AND AIMS

TARGET AUDIENCES

KEY MESSAGES

COMMS CHANNELS

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TIMELINE AND MILESTONES

MEASURE AND REPORTS

KEY MESSAGES

- Reinforce collaboration between institutes
- Landmark partnership between 38 laboratories and institutes across 19 member states in Europe
- Interdisciplinary, integrative and international approach to One Health is essential
- Opportunities for harmonisation of approaches, methodologies, databases and procedures.
- Develop sustainable programmes and projects.

GOVERNANCE

Ensuring all members understand the goals and objectives of the Communications Strategy to enable us to disseminate the information effectively.

MEASURE AND REPORT

Assess the effectiveness of the strategy and comms channels. Amend the strategy accordingly to ensure maximum alignment with audience and objectives for best results.

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AUDIENCE	INFORMATION	COMMS FUNCTION	COMMS OBJECTIVE	COMMS CHANNEL
OHEJP Partners	All internal (including confidential) and external communications	Maintain good relationships and lines of communication	Foster integrative and collaborative work approaches Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes Demonstrate use of funds	Website, social media, newsletters, email marketing, editorial, conferences, PR
Stakeholders	Internal and external (relevant) communications	Maintain good relationships and lines of communication	Transparency of project and progress Demonstrate use of Grant Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes	Website, social media, newsletters, editorial, conferences, PR
Policy Makers	External communications	Brand awareness Foster relationships to grow network Sustainability of project To affect change	To inform and open dialogue Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes	Social media, website, external newsletter, editorial, PR
International bodies	External communications	Brand awareness Foster relationships to grow network Sustainability of project To affect change	To inform and open dialogue Demonstrate OHEJP impact/scientific outcomes	Social media, website, external newsletter, editorial, PR
Scientists - external	External professional communications	Brand awareness Foster relationships	To inform	Social media, editorial, website, external news, email marketing, networking, conferences, PR
Healthcare Professionals - external	External professional communications	Brand awareness. Foster relationships	To inform	Social media, editorial, website, external news, email marketing, networking, conferences, PR
Students, Early Career Researchers	External communications	Brand awareness. Create the next generation of OHEJP collaborators and One Health scientists	To inform, educate and inspire	Social media, website, editorial, email marketing, networking, conferences
General Public	Jargon-free external communications	Image building, brand awareness	To inform and educate	Social media, website, newsletter, editorial, PR

OHEJP EVENTS

Throughout the lifetime of the OHEJP there are a number of events, including the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM), Cogwheel workshops, Stakeholders Committee Meetings, other OHEJP project workshops and the WP6 Education and Training Activities such as the OHEJP Summer School, the ASM Satellite Workshop, the Continuing Professional Development module and the Communication and Media workshop.

Communication for OHEJP Events:

There are many OHEJP events throughout the consortium which need to be documented to demonstrate the activity of the OHEJP and also to encourage participation from consortium members.

The Communication Team at Surrey aim to showcase more OHEJP events on the dedicated [events page](#) of the website. To achieve this a [OHEJP Communications mailbox](#) has been created. The objective of this is to ensure that this email address is copied into any meeting requests (i.e. PMT meetings, SSB meetings, POC meetings, PMC meetings etc.) and any events organised by consortium members.

The Communication Team will monitor this mailbox and input any appropriate events and meetings into the OHEJP events calendar on the website. Additionally, event organisers can create events on the OHEJP website using the 'My Events' tab at the top of the page. Here organisers can add all of the details of their events, images and any other relevant information.

Although this page is monitored regularly by the CO, **it is important that event organisers email the Communication Team to let them know that the event has been submitted online.** This will allow them to appropriately advertise the event, internally and externally to the consortium and to promote attendance to events and meetings, **where appropriate.** For example, open events will be widely advertised to wide audiences on our online platforms, however, closed meetings such as the Stakeholders' Committee Meeting not be advertised to a wide audience. It should be stated on the event description (for the purpose of the website) that these meetings are "*by invitation only*". Furthermore, detailed information for these events will not be published online.

For open events, the event details will be advertised on several platforms:

1. The OHEJP website (front end and in the private space)
2. Email communication to appropriate consortium mailing lists
3. OHEJP social media platforms
4. OHEJP newsletters
5. Institute websites (where appropriate)
6. Collaborator or Stakeholder websites (where appropriate)

This increased awareness of events across the consortium will ensure that all events are communicated about in advance and that events and dissemination of the OHEJP is correctly reported (see 'Reporting on OHEJP Events' section below).

Communication at OHEJP Annual Scientific Meetings:

The Communication Team at University of Surrey will have a communication stand at each of the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meetings. This aims to raise the profile of the OHEJP to a captive audience.

During this event, the Communication Team will promote the OHEJP and all of the events and opportunities that the consortium brings. Furthermore, they will be on hand to provide support for the OHEJP website and any other needs of consortium members. This will be an excellent opportunity to promote OHEJP events, workshops and open WP6 calls to gain interest for organising events such as the Summer School, CPD module, Communication and Media Workshop and to raise the profile of the OHEJP annual Short Term Missions.

The OHEJP Twitter account will be a very active platform at these events with a designated hashtag (#OHEJPASM2019, (#OHEJPASM2020, (#OHEJPASM2021, (#OHEJPASM2022). This will not only document the event in real time, but also promote One Health discussions on Twitter and encourage collaborations. LinkedIn will be used less frequently and will focus on key messages and speakers, in addition to posting summaries and key highlights. All attendees are encouraged to use this hashtag and tag @OneHealthEJP.

An array of merchandise will be available for each ASM, including pens, notepads, post-it notes, USB sticks, lanyards and flyers to give more information about the OHEJP.

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@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

What services can the Communication Team provide to local ASM organisers?

- Provide the OHEJP branding guide and high-quality images (logos, Venn diagrams)
- Help with the creation of flyers
- Support with the ASM specific merchandise to make sure the OHEJP logos and colours are used effectively
- Disseminate information regarding the event. This can be achieved several different ways:
 - Emailing internal mailing lists about the event
 - Advertising the event on the OHEJP website and social media platforms
 - Advertise the event in consortium and external newsletters
 - Live tweeting during the event to raise the profile online
 - Promote the sponsors of the event
 - Promotion of social events and/or sightseeing

Checklist for local ASM organisers:

- Establish contacts with the OHEJP Communication Team
- Branding adheres to the OHEJP branding guide
- Does the website and all ASM merchandise contain the OHEJP logo and colours?
- Do your sponsor packages include social media advertisement of the companies sponsoring the event? If so, let the Communication Team know in advance
- Have you made provisions for a Communication Team booth at the event?
 - Have you given the Communication Team a shipping address for OHEJP merchandise to arrive ahead of the ASM?
- Have you given **all** key date to the Communication Team?
 - Dates of the event
 - Dates of any social events
 - Dates of Early Bird registration
 - Dates of standard registration
 - Closure of registration

Communication of and at other OHEJP events:

The Communication Team is available to help promote any OHEJP events within the consortium and to a wider audience. Furthermore, the Communication Team can provide the OHEJP branding guide and logos etc to help with the branding of events. Where appropriate, the Communication Team can check event flyers and provide guidance on branding.

All events can be promoted on the website, Twitter, LinkedIn and in the OHEJP newsletters. The success of this will rely on early contact and discussion with the Communication Team.

Promoting the event in 'real-time' is also an important part of the OHEJP communication strategy as it demonstrates that our consortium is active and collaborating with a wide range of scientists, partners and stakeholders etc. Therefore, the Communication Team aims to attend, or remotely promote any event organised within the consortium. If the Communication Team cannot attend the event in person, they will rely on images and content being provided to them during the event. If this is organised in advanced, the Communication Team and event organiser can agree a live Tweeting schedule for the event.

In order to help event organisers with the preparation of events, the Communication Team has provided the below checklist of how they can help with your event:

- Have you registered your event on the OHEJP website using the 'My Events' function at the top of the page (this can only be done once you have logged in)?
- Have you contacted the Communication Team (OHEJPCommunications@surrey.ac.uk) to make them aware of your event?
- If you cannot add the event to the website, the Communication Team will do this for you
 - Have you provided the Communication Team with the relevant content and images for them to do this?
- Have you discussed with the Communication Team how you would like to advertise the event?
- Have you discussed with the Communication Team if you would like to live Tweet the event?
- Have you discussed with the Communication Team if you would like to provide a post for the OHEJP website following the event?
 - This can be to discuss its success, outcomes or any other important information
- Have you discussed your merchandise requirements ahead of the event? The Communication Team can post merchandise to you!

Reporting of OHEJP Events:

The OHEJP has an [Internal Events Survey](#) on the OHEJP website. This survey has been designed by the OHEJP Support Team in order for OHEJP events to be reported to the European Commission. This survey should be completed by **anyone** in the consortium who has **organised** a OHEJP event or **attended** a OHEJP event. Additionally, this survey should be completed by any member of the consortium that has **presented** the OHEJP at any events. This is to ensure that the dissemination efforts of consortium members are accurately reported.

Consortium members have been made aware of this survey through the website, emails and the OHEJP January Consortium Newsletter. However, increased awareness of this survey is required. This could be achieved through the following routes:

1. Contacting project leaders and requesting that they inform their researchers of the requirement to fill out this survey.
2. The Support Team should emphasise the importance of this survey.
3. The Communications Team at Surrey should post updates on the private space of the website and send email reminders to consortium members.
4. At all OHEJP events and meetings, the survey should be advertised on the final slide of any presentation given.
5. The survey should be mentioned in consortium newsletters to remind members to complete.

Branding for OHEJP Events:

To ensure that the branding for all of these OHEJP associated events is consistent, it is important that the organisers of these events use the branding guide detailed in this document. Creating a strong brand for the OHEJP will not only make the programme more recognisable at conferences and events but will support the WP7 Sustainability goals. It is also essential that event organisers have a close relationship with the OHEJP Communication Teams.

The Communication Team's role in OHEJP events is to help to align the branding of all communication tools for the event, in addition to assisting with the promotion of events through the OHEJP website, Twitter account and LinkedIn accounts. The Communication Team has access to mailing lists of consortium members and a network of Communication Contact Persons (CCPs) in each institute in the OHEJP consortium which is internally led by the Communication Team. Direct contact with consortium members will ensure that each member is informed of OHEJP event and benefits as a member. Promotion of events to wider audiences on the website and social media platforms will ensure that those external to the consortium may also attend events, this will increase the awareness of the OHEJP and educate a future generation with an awareness and understanding of One Health.

If events do not have a designated communications budget, the Communication Team can work with the event organisers to create "Save the Date" announcements and any flyers and merchandise required. The Communication Team will require close communication regarding these requests and should be informed of the necessary requirements as soon as possible (key contact: e.camplimg@surrey.ac.uk). This will ensure that all communication tools are designed to a high quality and there is sufficient time to advertise the event.

Event Registration on the OHEJP Website:

Registration for OHEJP meetings will be completed using the events tool on the website. The Coordination Team will oversee this with help from the Communication Team as necessary. Using the website will streamline the meeting registration process and also encourage the use of the website by consortium members. Using this facility will also ensure that all OHEJP meetings are accurately shown on the 'News and Events' page of the website.

The Coordination Team will need to add the event to the website, in addition to creating tickets for the event where people can register. If the event is on the OHEJP website (i.e. a public platform) anyone can register for this event. Therefore, it is important that Coordination monitor this can send the necessary links to the individuals requested to attend the event. The Communication Team has provided the Coordination Team a document to explain how to do this and guidance on how members can register for events.

A limitation of the events registration facility on the website is that the functionality only works if the organiser is an administrator on the website. This is therefore limited to the Coordination Team and the Communication Team for security reasons. It is therefore recommended that event organisers arrange

and manage their own event registration on an alternative platform. Despite this, **event organisers are required to add their event/workshop/webinar etc to the OHEJP events page AND contact the Communication Team who can advertise the website to a wider audience.**

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For Work Package 6 workshops such as the ASM Satellite workshop, it is recommended that the WP6 Project Manager and organisers work with the ASM organisers to ensure a registration facility for attendance to this workshop is available from the ASM website when delegates register to attend the ASM.

For events where registration is on the OHEJP website, we will have a field for individuals to tell the Communication Team where they found out about the event. For example, on Twitter, LinkedIn, the OHEJP website, email etc. This will allow the Communications Team to monitor the success of event promotion and to evaluate which method of advertisement is most successful to different audiences.

OHEJP MERCHANDISE

OHEJP merchandise has been created in line with the OHEJP Branding Guide (above). Merchandise will be available to all OHEJP events including the Annual Scientific Meeting, WP6 events, workshops and meetings. A representative from the Communication Team will attend OHEJP PMT, SSB, POC, PMC meetings, and can therefore take pens, notepads etc. to these meetings to distribute. These can also be distributed during JIP and JRP annual meetings to ensure that OHEJP researchers receive these items.

The Communication Team will contact PMT members, Institute Representatives, JRP and JIP Project Leaders, meeting organisers and event organisers regarding their need for merchandise. The Communication Team would like to encourage these consortium members to disseminate the OHEJP merchandise and will approach members and ask if they would like to receive a box of merchandise for their institute. ANSES and Sciensano will also be provided with boxes of merchandise as they are the coordinators of the OHEJP and should distribute merchandise at any meetings or events they host or attend (where appropriate).

For the OHEJP ASM, the Communication Team will post merchandise to the organising committee to include in the conference bags two weeks before the event, in addition to providing merchandise for a dedicated OHEJP Communications desk (see 'Communication at OHEJP Annual Scientific Meetings' section for more information).

At other OHEJP events such as the Satellite Workshop, Summer School, CPD module and Communication and Media workshop merchandise will also be available. This will be discussed with the organisers of each event. It is stipulated in the WP6 call guidelines that organisers are to contact the Communication Team for any assistance they may require early in the organisation of events.

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Available merchandise will include:	
OHEJP pens	Gifts for invited speakers (OHEJP Bluetooth speakers)
OHEJP notepads	OHEJP USB sticks
OHEJP post-it notes	OHEJP tote bag
OHEJP lanyards	Pin with OHEJP logo: helps Identify the Community

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